

Transformative Social Innovation Strategy

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background and context

Over the last decade, the European Union and its member states have significantly advanced their adaptation policy frameworks as a response to the growing urgency of climate change impacts. International agreements and milestones, such as the Paris Agreement's global adaptation goal outlined in Article 7 (UNFCCC, 2016) and the financial commitments made at COP26 (UNFCCC, 2021), have shaped global ambitions and provided an impetus for action. Within this context, the EU has positioned itself as a frontrunner (Jordan et al., 2012), aiming to align its policies with these international frameworks and setting high standards for global adaptation governance. Early EU climate policies focused primarily on reducing greenhouse gas emissions, following the IPCC First Assessment Report (1990). However, adaptation needs gained prominence over time, with early steps evident in sectoral policies and the European Climate Change Programme in the year 2000. A more coordinated approach emerged in 2009 with the publication of the "*White Paper on Adapting to Climate Change: Towards a European Framework for Action*" (2009), which proposed integrating adaptation measures into key EU policies and frameworks.

This momentum culminated in the EU Adaptation Strategy (2013), which laid the foundation for a comprehensive and structured approach towards climate resilience. The strategy encouraged member states to develop national adaptation plans, provided funding and technical guidance, while seeking integration of adaptation across broader EU policies, such as agriculture, fisheries, and regional development. It also enhanced decision-making through the establishment of the Climate-ADAPT platform, which supports policymakers with data and tools to implement adaptation measures effectively. These initiatives marked a significant step towards embedding adaptation considerations into the EU's policy landscape.

Building on these achievements, the updated EU Adaptation Strategy (2021), a key pillar of the European Green Deal, significantly raises the ambition and scope of adaptation efforts. It introduces binding, quantifiable goals to ensure measurable progress at both the EU and member state levels. The strategy also underscores the importance of international collaboration, extending support to partner countries and aligning EU adaptation efforts with global climate resilience priorities. Furthermore, it deepens the integration of adaptation across EU policies, linking it to initiatives such as the Circular Economy Action Plan (2020), the Biodiversity Strategy (2020), and the Farm-to-Fork Strategy (2020). The Adaptation Strategy also prioritises closing knowledge gaps, improving access to data through an upgraded Climate-ADAPT platform, and promoting nature-based solutions (NbS)

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as cost-effective and sustainable measures to enhance climate resilience while delivering multiple co-benefits for biodiversity, ecosystems, and human well-being.

The updated Adaptation Strategy strengthens the emphasis on systemic change, resilience, and a whole-society approach to adaptation (Henstra, 2016). It recognises that action is needed on every level – local, regional, national, and EU – and involves a wide range of stakeholders, including academia, industry, government, civil society, and environmental actors. This focus on decentralised action is particularly important for translating adaptation plans into practical implementation. Local and regional authorities play a pivotal role in fostering public engagement, tailoring adaptation measures to specific contexts, and driving grassroots action (Rauken et al., 2015). Alliances such as the Global Covenant of Mayors illustrate the growing importance of adaptation networks in facilitating collaboration, knowledge exchange, and collective progress.

While the EU's Adaptation Strategy marks a significant step forward, challenges persist. Adaptation policies remain fragmented, and inconsistent political will – often influenced by electoral cycles and public opinion – limits the comprehensive implementation of long-term strategies (Biesbroek et al., 2010; Remling, 2018). To address these gaps, transformative approaches that go beyond incremental adjustments are necessary. These approaches should focus on social and systemic innovations that encourage new models of collaboration, community engagement, and adaptive practices (Leiter, 2023; UNEP, 2022). The RESIST project exemplifies this approach, with its emphasis on regional and local governance as catalysts for transformative change. By empowering administrations with the tools, resources, and authority to implement place-based adaptation measures, the project is an example of how to drive climate adaptation on the subnational level.

As Europe is confronted with increasingly tangible impacts of climate change, there is a growing need for proactive and transformative adaptation efforts. The evolution of the EU's adaptation policies reflects a growing commitment to addressing these challenges, however, there is much more to be done. The path forward requires bold, innovative solutions rooted in collaboration, inclusivity, and systemic change, ensuring that Europe remains at the forefront of global efforts to build a sustainable, climate-resilient, and inclusive future (Ulibarri et al., 2022).

1.2 Purpose and scope of the report

Generally, RESIST establishes a framework for the project regions to implement Large-Scale Demonstrators (LSDs), enabling the experimentation and validation of innovative adaptation solutions. These solutions combine technological tools, social measures, incentives, and regulatory policy instruments to enhance resilience in the face of regional climate change challenges. The RESIST approach addresses key aspects of governance, societal needs, citizen behaviours, and

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public and financial priorities, which offer comprehensive pathways to climate adaptation. Thus, at the heart of RESIST are the LSD activities, which focus on testing and demonstrating innovative approaches to tackling climate hazards and vulnerabilities. These initiatives aim to build more climate-resilient regions and are implemented in four regions: Southwest Finland, Central Denmark, Catalonia, and Central Portugal.

While these kinds of adaptation efforts normally remain small and fragmented, as highlighted by the IPCC (2022), and thus risk failing to achieve broader, systemic impact, the RESIST project recognises the critical need to overcome barriers for implementation, scaling and replication as a way to maximise the impact of the project's pilot activities. In this context, the **Transformative Social Innovation (TSI) strategy provides a framework to maximise the social impacts of LSD activities**. TSI provides a lens through which the regional adaptation processes and governance can be understood as a process of systemic change that depends on the orchestration of change in four key focus areas for leveraging RESIST activities, enabling LSD regions to drive innovation while fostering collaboration across stakeholders and sectors. Addressing these areas, can foster a dynamic interplay between technological innovation and societal transformation, and as such TSI offers an opportunity to address the complexities of adaptation with a systemic perspective.

The TSI aims to align the activities of the LSDs with broader theories and processes of societal change while harnessing and building up the capacities of regional stakeholders to collectively and sustainably manage transformative change. They provide the foundation for this transformation by **recommending strategic actions in the four key focus areas of dynamics within the LSD, network formation, catalysing institutional change, and the alteration of the socio-material context**, which ultimately contribute to challenging entrenched norms and fostering systemic transformation. Subsequently, the TSI framework provides strategic action points for the LSD teams to align technological and societal change processes.

Based on a novel theoretical understanding and framework, we engaged regional partners in identifying the most present issues in these categories. These points have been identified based on information retrieved from regional partners during interviews, focus groups and direct feedback on previous iterations of this report. Through the aggregation of regional challenges and potential solutions we elaborated the strategic actions as basis for the development of measures to maximise the impact of the LSD work. These actions aim to support **an impact-oriented change process that aims at reducing regional vulnerabilities and building transformative capacities within the regional governance system**. This process is necessarily open-ended, depending on changes on multiple levels, and thus going beyond the work implemented in the context of RESIST. However, in cooperation and with the support of the transversal partners like ZSI, among others, these strategic actions will be finetuned, prioritised, and contextualised to develop recommendations for regional

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implementation by the LSD teams (see section 4.2). A report on the social innovation process (D4.1.3) will summarise the experiences made during the remaining three years of the RESIST project.

1.3 Structure of the report

The rest of the report is structured as follows. The **second chapter explores the foundational theories and concepts that guided the development of this report**. The chapter introduces concepts that underpin climate change adaptation and TSI. It defines key concepts such as adaptation pathways, integration across sectors, resilience, and vulnerability. Additionally, it outlines the theoretical foundations of TSI, emphasising its role in driving systemic change through innovation, agency, and empowerment. The chapter also explores the barriers and enablers of transformative adaptation, highlighting how institutional inertia and resource constraints can hinder progress, while participatory governance and co-production of knowledge serve as critical enablers.

The **third chapter provides the synthesis of these theoretical concepts into a common methodology** that provides the basis for the development of the regional strategies. The chapter presents the methodology which is a relational approach building on four key focus areas, that provides the blueprint for the TSI for each LSD region. This methodology strives to integrate transformative concepts, social innovation, and thinking from climate adaptation practices. It emphasises participatory governance, collective empowerment, and network formation to address regional vulnerabilities and foster resilience. Further, the second section provides information on the development process and data collection methods, including interviews and workshops, as basis for understanding local contexts and co-creating adaptive strategies.

The **fourth chapter contains the synthesis based on the research on the regional demonstrators** – Southwest Finland, Central Denmark, Catalonia, and Central Portugal. It introduces the regional adaptation challenges, approaches and solutions of the LSDs and a synthesis of the strategic actions defined for each key focus area. A total of eleven strategic actions are introduced. Based on this overview, an outlook is provided that exemplifies the implementation process of these actions with the RESIST project. The **final fifth chapter concludes the report**.

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2 Theoretical considerations

2.1 Introduction to climate change adaptation and transformative social innovation

Climate actions are urgent and necessary. Scientific consensus clearly indicates three key messages: 1) climate change is happening and becoming worse, 2) the impacts are costly, both economically and in terms of damages to ecosystem functioning and human wellbeing, and 3) technology, science, and policy innovations can help society mitigate carbon emissions and adapt to change (Owen, 2020). Thus, climate actions are required on both the causes and consequences of climate change. While mitigation describes addressing climate change via a drastic reduction in greenhouse gas emissions, **adaptation refers to actions that help reduce vulnerability** to the current or expected impacts of climate change like weather extremes and hazards, sea-level rise, biodiversity loss, or food and water insecurity.

While some progress has been achieved in terms of climate mitigation, e.g., with regards to electricity, there remain significant challenges in the societal systems of transport, heating, construction, and agriculture. With the effects of climate change becoming more severe during the last years, there is also the need to accelerate climate change adaptation efforts – with the EU adaptation strategy (EC, 2021), emphasising the need to adapt smarter, faster, and more systemic.

Climate change adaptation generally aims at “*managing the unavoidable*” by strengthening resilience and **adaptive capacity to climate-induced impacts** already underway or expected (Matos et al., 2022). The IPCC (2014) synthesis report describes adaptation as the process of adjustment to actual or expected climate and its effects. It is not a one-time emergency response, but **a series of proactive measures** to deal with the nexus of hazard (e.g. drought, sea level rise), exposure (e.g. less water in the South), and vulnerability (e.g. poverty or lack of education). The adaptation concept, thus, combines adverse exposure to climate change effects with social vulnerabilities and provides a developmental direction in adjusting socio-ecological systems in response to actual or expected climatic stimuli (Harding et al., 2024).

Adaptation activities will have immediate and gradual impacts on social, economic, political, and environmental systems (Owen, 2020). However, adaptation is also not a static concept but can be distinguished between **anticipatory adaptation** that aims at reducing biophysical and socio-economic risk, or **reactive anticipation**, which strive to minimise costs of emergency responses (Matos et al., 2022). Further, its scope can be **incremental or transformative** (see section 2.2) and

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as such, a variety of actions can contribute to effective adaptation. Owen (2020) further distinguishes between **social adaptation** activities, e.g., educational, informational, and behavioural actions, **institutional adaptation** activities, e.g., economic options, laws and regulations, policies and programmes, as well as physical and **structural adaptation** activities, e.g., engineered and built environments, technological innovations, ecosystem-based adaptations, or services.

One general criticism in the adaptation field is that actions remain too incremental and are not implemented at the scale, depth, and speed needed to avoid risks (IPCC, 2022) and subsequently might lead to unsustainable or maladaptive changes (Fedele et al., 2019). Thus, there is a **need to prioritise transformative adaptation** approaches that overcome vested interests, economic lock-ins, institutional path dependencies and prevalent practices, cultures, norms and belief systems (Harding et al., 2024; IPCC, 2022). As such, transformative adaptation goes beyond singular interventions and technological fixes but requires systemic approaches that take socio-ecological and socio-technical structures and their vulnerabilities into account.

Thus, there is a need to improve the integration of social concepts into our understanding of adaptation as a basis to widen their scope and accelerate their implementation. **Transformative Social Innovation** (Avelino et al., 2019; Castro-Arce & Vanclay, 2020; Pel et al., 2020) provides a framework to understand how social dimensions can contribute to challenge, alter, or disrupt dominant social structures, policies, and practices in response to socio-ecological and socio-technical challenges. While social innovation, following Moulaert et al. (2013), can be understood as the creation, renewal or transformation of social relations in the development of new ways of working together to achieve societal goals, the concept of transformative social innovation **interlinks social processes on different levels of aggregation**: individual and collective empowerment within change initiatives, network formation, institutional change, and changing societal framework conditions (Pel et al., 2020). Through these four levels, transformative social innovation provides a relational framework that is grounded in current debates on transformative social change, transformative innovation, and transformative change.

Transformative social innovation, thus, is part of a set of new approaches like transformative innovation policy (Haddad et al., 2022; Schot & Steinmueller, 2018), mission-oriented approaches (Hekkert et al., 2020; Mazzucato, 2018; Wanzenböck et al., 2020), or system-innovation (Grin, 2020; OECD, 2015) that go beyond solving immediate problems and aim at creating systemic change in social, economic, and political systems. These approaches all highlight the **need for rethinking and reshaping existing socio-technical systems** to create more sustainable and inclusive societies. These approaches stress the importance of empowerment, inclusivity, experimentation, and a willingness to revisit existing arrangements to tackle societal challenges effectively.

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This thinking strongly builds upon socio-technical reasoning following the **multi-level perspective** (Geels, 2004) as a process model. Explained in detail in section 3.4, this perspective argues that the human systems of production and consumption are organised in stable socio-technical regimes, which consist of technology, industry, markets, policy, science, and culture. Innovative approaches, may it be products, processes, services, or organisations (OECD, 2018), emerge in **niches and face uphill struggles** against existing systems that are reproduced, maintained, incrementally improved, and regulated by incumbent actors such as firms, engineers, users, and policymakers (Geels, 2024). Subsequently, **socio-technical regimes are stabilised by lock-ins** that make them resistant to radical change. Transformative social innovation and transformative innovation policy provide a perspective on the governance of niche formation, maturation, and generalisation of novel approaches incl. social innovation (Weber et al., 2024) and are, thus, well suited to address the root causes of climate vulnerability.

Subsequently, we argue that transformative adaptation and transformative social innovation are concepts that combined provide a theoretically grounded and process-oriented approach to addressing regional vulnerabilities through new forms of governance and cooperation between actors of the quintuple helices. Hence, the regional transformative social innovation strategies **combine the perspectives of adaptation as a response to place-based vulnerabilities and transformative social innovation as a mechanism for social-ecological and socio-technical transformation**, that goes beyond incremental change.

2.2 Core concepts in climate change adaptation

The complexity of climate adaptation lies in effectively coordinating resources, facilitating knowledge exchange, and aligning the interests of diverse stakeholders across sectors and regions. Successful adaptation measures must be sustainable, resilient, and adaptable to address both current and future vulnerabilities, ultimately safeguarding ecosystems, communities, and economies. A comprehensive understanding of adaptation demands an exploration of the key principles and challenges shaping the current discourse. In the following sections, we will examine foundational concepts and emerging insights in adaptation, providing a nuanced view of the strategies necessary to build resilient societies in the face of accelerating climate risks (Owen, 2020).

2.2.1 Adaptation pathways and trajectories

Adaptation measures should be sustainable, robust, and capable of addressing both current and future vulnerabilities. They should ultimately safeguard ecosystems, economies, and societies. Many studies on adaptation emphasise the fact that **current adaptation efforts often have a fragmented and incremental character** (Berrang-Ford et al., 2021). As a result, adaptation efforts often remain

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limited in scale, sector-specific, and primarily aimed at addressing current impacts or near-term risks (Masseti & Mendelsohn, 2018). To address this problem, the **concept of transformation** has become increasingly prominent in the climate adaptation literature (Filho et al., 2023).

The IPCC defines what it calls “transformational adaptation” as “*adaptation that changes the fundamental attributes of a socio-ecological system in anticipation of climate change and its impacts*” (IPCC, 2023: 170). Contrasting it to incremental adaptation, transformative **transformation is often famed as a fundamental system change** that mobilises societal resources on all levels (Fedele et al., 2019). Thus, the focus on transformation reflects a distinctive level and depth of change, driven by values and principles like equity and justice (Gram-Hanssen et al., 2023). Also, it emphasises that adaptation should not only accommodate changes but also **contest existing realities and create new alternatives** (Pelling, 2010). Neither incremental nor transformative adaptation is typically seen as a single, isolated approach. Instead, they are often viewed as a set of interrelated processes that can be either deliberate and planned or reactive to significant, sometimes unforeseen changes (Lonsdale et al., 2015).

Also, one major issue in these efforts is the **high level of uncertainty** that surrounds adaptation efforts (Dessai et al., 2009; Skinner et al., 2014). Addressing this challenge, **pathways approaches** to adaptation are used to increase flexibility and long-term planning, allowing systems to navigate multiple potential futures as climate conditions and available solutions change (Van Der Brugge & Roosjen, 2015). Rather than following a single trajectory, a pathways approach focuses on creating adaptive strategies that can be adjusted or shifted over time based on emerging risks, opportunities, and feedback from ongoing developments (Werners et al., 2021). By mapping out a range of potential scenarios, communities, institutions, and ecosystems can develop incremental and transformative actions, choosing paths that **maintain resilience while leaving room for course corrections** (Haasnoot et al., 2013). This approach promotes continuous learning, stakeholder engagement, and the integration of diverse knowledge systems, ensuring that adaptation is dynamic and responsive (Wise et al., 2014). Furthermore, pathways approaches are also praised for their effectiveness as a foresight tool that considers uncertainties to help mitigate the adverse impacts of climate change (Fazey et al., 2016). This kind of **long-term thinking and planning** are essential to ensure that adaptation measures remain effective as climate conditions continue to evolve. In essence, the pathways approach helps systems remain agile, enabling proactive decision-making that aligns short-term actions with long-term resilience goals (Lawrence & Haasnoot, 2017).

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2.2.2 Integration across sectors

Because of the multidimensional character of climate impacts, adaptation efforts often need to **cut across a wide range of sectors** (Leck & Simon, 2013). Common examples of such sectors are agriculture, water management, infrastructure development, public health, disaster preparedness, and so on. Therefore, adaptation measures require **multilevel coordination and collaboration** among decision-makers responsible for different sectors (Ishtiaque, 2021). For instance, there is a need to align policies related to water resources with those concerning agriculture and urban planning to ensure a comprehensive and integrated approach. Furthermore, on a local level it requires **alignment with national adaptation initiatives**, which in turn need to be in line with international agreements and frameworks, such as the Paris Agreement (Hauge et al., 2018).

Furthermore, adaptation efforts also involve a **wide range of relevant actors**, including national and local governments, international organisations, NGOs, and private sector entities. It is an obvious challenge to involve these actors in developing and implementing climate adaptation policies (Petzold et al., 2023). Therefore, **establishing or strengthening institutions, rules, and organisations** to handle adaptation efforts represent an important aim of transformative adaptation pathways (Glaas et al., 2010). This also involves building the capacity of institutions to effectively plan and implement adaptation measures (Storbjörk & Hedrén, 2011). Also, the development and enforcement of legal frameworks and regulations that support adaptation efforts is necessary, alongside securing adequate funding and resources for these initiatives (Smith et al., 2016; Zahar et al., 2012).

Finally, achieving comprehensive approaches not only helps mitigate the immediate impacts of climate change but also **strengthens the overall capacity of societies to adapt to future challenges** (Dewulf et al., 2015). This requires synergies across sectors, ensuring that strategies in areas from agriculture to urban planning and public health are interlinked (Hedensted Lund et al., 2012). In this process, the private sector plays a key role by investing in innovative solutions, such as green infrastructure or climate-smart technologies, that can drive resilience at scale (Klein et al., 2018; Schneider, 2014). Moreover, **community-based adaptation initiatives are essential**, as they bring local knowledge and needs into the planning process, making strategies more effective and context-specific.

2.2.3 Resilience and adaptive capacity

Resilience is key in the context of climate adaptation and its dynamics of change (Davidson et al., 2016). As a concept, it entails a focus on enabling social, economic, and environmental systems to absorb disturbances and reorganise without collapsing, even as they undergo significant disruption

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(Folke, 2016). Considering climate impacts like extreme weather, resource scarcity, and shifting ecosystems, the first focus is on **maintaining the core functions of systems** (Field et al., 2012). Thus, the challenges to existing structures are countered by adapting, redistributing resources, and evolving in response. This entails different measures in different contexts. For example, resilient economies diversify to reduce reliance on vulnerable sectors, while resilient social systems foster collaboration and support to enhance community response. In the context of environmental systems, biodiversity and ecosystem services can help to focus on regeneration and continued functioning despite disturbances.

Closely related to the concept of resilience is the notion of **adaptive capacity**. This is vital for communities, institutions, and ecosystems to respond to climate risks in innovative ways that maintain and improve their resilience and sustainability in the face of climate risks. It refers to the ability to not only respond to immediate disruptions but also to the anticipation of future risks, allowing systems to evolve in ways that reduce vulnerabilities (Boyd et al., 2015). This adaptability ensures that systems can **not only withstand climate impacts but also emerge stronger and more resilient**. One key element is to foster diversity in both social and ecological systems, which enhances adaptability to a wide range of future scenarios (Turner et al., 2022). Institutional flexibility is also crucial, allowing for experimentation, learning, and the integration of new insights into governance structures (Amaru & Chhetri, 2013). Collaboration across sectors – public, private, and civil society – is essential for aligning policies and actions that support adaptive capacity.

Ideally, this leads to a form of transformative resilience, which aims for systems to **fundamentally shift**, becoming more adaptive, equitable, and sustainable (Pelling, 2010). This requires identifying and addressing the underlying vulnerabilities and inequalities that make systems fragile in the first place (Wilson et al., 2020). Also here, it is important to engage local communities in co-developing solutions that meet their needs while also addressing long-term sustainability goals (Schlosberg et al., 2017). Additionally, the use of anticipatory governance frameworks can enable systems to not only respond to current risks but also **proactively shape desirable futures** by integrating foresight, innovation, and social equity into decision-making processes.

2.2.4 Vulnerability and risk reduction

Understanding and framing climate vulnerabilities is a pivotal part of any adaptation strategy (Brooks, 2003). Identifying specific climate impacts and their definition – e.g. as environmental, economic, or social issues – can significantly shape the responses to climate change (Birkmann et al., 2013). A thorough understanding of risk and vulnerabilities is essential, among other things, for effectively defining policy problems and prioritising adaptation actions (Smit & Wandel, 2006). By framing vulnerabilities accurately and inclusively, policymakers can define interventions that

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enhance resilience, allocate resources more efficiently, and foster collaborative efforts across sectors and communities (Arthurson & Baum, 2015). In this process, **the construction of normative principles** can help to guide problem-solving and institution-building around climate adaptation (Gorddard et al., 2016). This can for instance help in ensuring that that adaptation measures are equitable and effective, targeting the most at-risk populations and addressing their unique needs.

A crucial step in the planning of adaptation strategies is **climate risk assessment**, which involves evaluating the **probability and severity of harmful outcomes resulting from climate change**. In most cases, the assessments focuses on the interplay between exposure to hazards, the sensitivity of systems, and their adaptive capacity (Jurgilevich et al., 2017). As such, moves beyond identifying vulnerabilities by quantifying the likelihood of different impacts and their potential consequences. Exposure refers to the degree to which a community, ecosystem, or economy is subjected to climate hazards, while system sensitivity reflects how these systems respond to those exposures. Together, these elements can be used to **determine the overall risk**, underscoring the need for targeted strategies that reduce both exposure and sensitivity while enhancing resilience. Tools used for climate risk assessment often include climate models, impact simulations, and vulnerability mapping, which help predict future hazards and assess system responses under varying scenarios (Šedová et al., 2024). These tools enable decision-makers to visualise risks, prioritise interventions, and design adaptive strategies based on evidence-driven insights into potential outcomes.

Successful adaptation involves complex, strategic processes that redefine our approach to climate resilience by focusing on system-wide, long-term changes. This **goes beyond simply addressing immediate risks** – it requires the integration of innovative technologies, redesigning infrastructure, and reforming policies to support resilience on a broader scale. **Learning and adaptation are a continuous process**, with feedback loops enabling the assessment of progress and the adjustment of strategies as conditions evolve (Berrang-Ford et al., 2019). Crucially, transformative efforts demand more than technical solutions; these solutions need to be combined with efforts that support collaboration, encourage experimentation, and ensure inclusivity at every level (Adenle et al., 2015). This not only helps to mitigate climate risks but also **creates opportunities to enhance the general sustainability and well-being of communities**.

As climate change moves forward, the critical question becomes how to **embed transformative thinking and actions** into societal structures, allowing for the deeper social shifts necessary to sustain long-term adaptation. The next chapter delves into the theories and approaches that underpin societal transformation, laying the groundwork for understanding how we can achieve the radical changes needed to build a more resilient future.

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2.3 Theoretical foundations of transformative social innovation

The urgency of building resilience in communities and regions highlights the need to foster innovations that not only advance technical solutions but also drive profound societal shifts. In this context, a transformative social innovation framework provides valuable insights into mechanisms that can accelerate adaptive capacity through change at multiple levels: technological, institutional, and social. This chapter explores core theoretical concepts underlying this approach, examining how innovation and transformative change intersect to challenge conventional practices and foster sustainable futures. By synthesising perspectives on social innovation, system change, socio-technical transitions, and empowerment, it aims to deepen understanding of the agency required to navigate and influence transformative pathways. Through this lens, transformative social innovation emerges as a vital strategy for achieving climate resilience, situating community-led actions within broader processes of systemic adaptation and reimagining regional futures.

2.3.1 Innovation and transformative change

Josef Schumpeter, the founding father of innovation theory, introduced the distinction between invention (a novel idea for how to do things) and innovation (carrying it out into practice). This perspective includes two different aspects of innovation – novelty and implementation. Novelty can be seen contextual and refer to something that is new to those that produce or use the innovation or simply offers new functionalities (Edler & Fagerberg, 2017). The implementation aspect of **innovation indicates the usage of novel concepts** and most of the time implies that it is a commercially successful application. In the context of climate change adaptation, innovation typically refers to the development and implementation of new ideas, practices, and solutions that address both environmental and social vulnerabilities posed by climate change. Traditionally, innovation focuses on improving efficiency or solving immediate problems, e.g., technological improvements or infrastructure adjustments. However, the narrow understanding of innovation from a pure economic perspective is increasingly challenged, especially, in the context of societal challenges like climate change (Coad et al., 2022; Schot & Steinmueller, 2018).

To effectively address climate change and other “wicked” problems, which are characterised as persistent, complex, unpredictable problems with poorly defined boundaries (Rittel & Webber, 1973), the concept of transformative change emerged (Grin et al., 2010; Haddad et al., 2022; Schot & Steinmueller, 2018). **Transformative change refers to a fundamental and radical shift in societal systems**, structures, and practices to address pressing challenges such as sustainability, inequality, and climate change. In adaptation, transformative change might imply to reimagine land-use policies to prevent overdevelopment in flood-prone areas while empowering local communities to manage their own risks, instead of simply improving flood defences. For instance, in coastal

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regions, transformative innovation might give fishing communities a leadership role in managing marine resources, aligning ecological sustainability with livelihoods. Whereas in rural areas, the inclusion of farmer communities in energy production might represent a novelty with potentially transformative impacts.

At the core, transformative change involves systematically rethinking and reshaping existing socio-technical systems and aligning development trajectories with societal goals. Transformative change requires a multidimensional governance and coordination approach that builds on experimentation, reflexive learning, and the capacity to adapt and learn from experiences (Haddad et al., 2022; Janssen et al., 2023; Schot & Steinmueller, 2018).

In these transformation and reconfiguration processes (Geels, 2024), **innovation can act as a catalyst for transformative change** by introducing new tools, frameworks, and relationships that challenge traditional practices. Whether through social innovation (e.g., new participatory governance approaches) or technological innovation (e.g., renewable energy systems), innovations have the agency to create pathways for society to move beyond reactive measures toward a more proactive, equitable, and resilient future.

2.3.2 Social innovation and system change

In the course of transformative thinking, concepts of social innovation, social practices, and socio-technical structure gained importance for the development and successful implementation of systemic innovations to address societal challenges (Moulaert et al., 2013; Schot & Steinmueller, 2018). While there is a plethora of definitions that emphasise different aspects of social innovation, in the context of transformative change an understanding that highlights the purpose of a novel approach seems to be appropriate. Thus, we understand social innovations as “*novel initiatives or novel combinations of known solutions, aimed at tackling a societal problem or creating new societal opportunities, applied in practice.*” (Havas et al., 2023). In this thinking, the distinction between technological and non-technological innovations loses relevance, as most innovations rely to some degree both on new technologies and new social practices.

Social innovations include new initiatives or combinations of initiatives, which can take the form of **ideas, products, services, or processes, that are applied in a social practice** and foster new types of relationships and opportunities. These innovations are designed not only to provide direct benefits to society (first-order benefits) but also to enhance society’s overall capacity to act (second-order benefits). As social challenges are resistant to conventional approaches to solving them due to their inherent uncertainty and complexity, social innovation can play a crucial and even leading

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role for making transformative change happen and in a socially acceptable - or even desirable - way (Weber et al., 2024).

Social innovation introduces new ways of doing, thinking, and organising (Wittmayer et al., 2022), which have the potential for **challenging the dominant structures, norms, and power relations** that often sustain vulnerability in the context of climate adaptation. They carry the potential to break with traditional social, governance, and institutional practices that tend to prioritise short-term solutions, leading to incremental or maladaptation. As such, they are characterised by empowering various communities, promote participatory governance, and redefine resource management. Thus, it is viewed as a **process of collective creation** where communities or groups develop new social practices. This process not only addresses immediate social needs but also contributes to broader social transformation by establishing new norms and practices within society (Howaldt et al., 2014). By providing alternatives, such as community-led adaptation strategies or decentralized renewable energy systems, social innovation opens pathways for transformative change. A successful development of social innovation, contributing to transformative change, requires changes in regards to social practice but also to the social structures consisting of organisational resource allocation and institutional frameworks (Smets et al., 2017). Consequently, the governance of these change processes, which must enable a co-evolutionary development of practices, organisations and institutions, is an essential element of the acceleration of climate change adaptation.

2.3.3 Socio-technical transitions and multi-level perspective

The main difference between traditional innovation approaches and novel conceptualisations is the evolutionary and institutional understanding of change (Geels, 2024). To understand transformative approaches, the central question is – **what is it that is being transformed?** In transition studies (Fünfschilling & Truffer, 2014; Geels, 2004; Grin et al., 2010) and transformative innovation policy studies (Ghosh et al., 2021; Haddad et al., 2022; Schot & Steinmueller, 2018), **transformative change refers to a profound shift in socio-technical systems** aimed at addressing complex societal challenges, such as climate change adaptation. In this context, socio-technical systems are understood as complex systems that encompass the interaction between society's social elements (people, institutions, cultures, practices) and technical components (technologies, infrastructures, tools), that are necessary to fulfil societal functions (e.g. transport, communication, nutrition) (Geels, 2004). These systems involve the **co-evolution of technology and society**, where technical innovations shape social behaviour, and social structures influence how technologies are developed, adopted, and used.

The dominate theoretical framework to study on transformative change is the **Multi-Level Perspective** (MLP), which was introduced by Geels (2004) and provides framework for

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understanding how transitions and transformations occur within socio-technical systems (see Figure 1. for an MLP version for social innovation). It focuses on the interactions between three distinct levels: niches, regimes, and the broader socio-technical landscape. At the **niche** level, (radical) innovations emerge and are experimented with in protected spaces outside the mainstream. These innovations often challenge established norms and practices but require shielding from market pressures and societal expectations to develop and mature. The **regime** represents the dominant, stable configuration of a socio-technical system, including its institutions, technologies, policies, and social norms. Regimes are characterised by their stable alignments of their socio-technical elements and thus resist to change. The **landscape** is the broader macro-level environment that shapes the conditions under which regimes and niches operate. It consists of slower-moving external factors like cultural values, political contexts, economic trends, and environmental changes, such as climate change or resource scarcity.

Transitions occur when niche innovations gain enough momentum and/or external pressures from the landscape (like political shifts or environmental crises) create opportunities to challenge the stability of the regime. As niches align with landscape pressures, they can disrupt and eventually transform the existing regime, leading to systemic change. In the context of **climate adaptation**, the MLP explains how small-scale, innovative approaches to adapting to climate change, which often begin at the niche level, can gradually disrupt entrenched systems and practices within the regime. When broader landscape factors, such as increasing climate-related disasters or shifts in public policy, intensify the need for adaptation, these niche innovations can spread and contribute to a larger transformation of socio-technical systems towards more resilient, sustainable practices.

In the context of social innovation, Weber et al. (2024) describe an ideal-type transition in the MLG framework as follows: **Early niche formation** starts when social innovators develop an idea that addresses a social need. Innovators go through trial and error, learning and unlearning to refine their approaches, which often leads to empowerment as the social need begins to be addressed. During this phase, new social relations among both, the innovators and with external supporters or experts, are being formed. As various social innovation initiatives emerge around the same need, they may begin interacting, either through cooperation and knowledge sharing or competition to differentiate their approaches.

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Figure 1: Multi-Level-Perspective for Social Innovations (Weber et al., 2024)

Successful approaches consolidate themselves through a **maturation** process that entails spreading through replication, adaptation, and support from promoters who provide resources and policy connections. Some initiatives grow while less successful ones may remain small or disappear. During this stage, innovations increasingly engage with the regime, seeking broader awareness and institutional change. This can lead to conflicts with entrenched regime actors resisting change, but successful social innovations may eventually reshape institutional frameworks, leading to their wider adoption and integration into mainstream systems. A successful **generalisation** of new approaches on regime level often requires windows of opportunity, e.g., shocks like extreme climate events or changes in frameworks like the implementation of the EU Missions (Geels & Schot, 2007; Sengers et al., 2019), and further entail the ending of certain practices, which is labelled as “exnovation”.

The generalisation of approaches, however, needs to overcome the systemic inertia that provide **resistance and lock-ins of existing regimes**. These lock-ins include techno-economic aspects like sunk investments, low-cost and high-performance of existing technologies. Social and cognitive lock-ins are rooted in routines, shared mindsets, and capabilities that guide actors’ perceptions and actions in particular ways, social networks that interdependent economic relations, or lifestyles that are formed around certain technologies and infrastructures. Institutional and political lock-ins include situations where existing policies favour incumbent actors and create an uneven playing field, or the privileged access of incumbent actors to decision making that could block support of radically new approaches (Geels, 2024). Overcoming these lock-ins requires ongoing and persistent actions from actors at various levels and with different positions and roles within these system (Grillitsch & Sotarauta, 2020).

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2.3.4 Agency and empowerment in social innovation

These actors' **agency** in transformation is central to driving systemic change, as it reflects the capacity of individuals and groups to actively challenge, shape, and redefine existing structures. In this context, human agency refers to intentional, purposive and meaningful actions, and the intended and unintended consequences of such actions (Grillitsch & Sotarauta, 2020) and the structures refers to the sum of physical, organisational, and institutional elements that comprise regional socio-technical systems. In the context of transformation, agency is understood as a **capacity for reorientation** within complex adaptive systems (Kok et al., 2021). This definition is influenced by Anthony Giddens' (1984) concept of agency, which emphasises that agency is not merely about the intentions of individuals but rather their capability to act in various ways within a given context.

In this understanding, **agency is relational**, meaning it arises from the interactions between actors and their environments. This relational understanding highlights that agency is not an inherent attribute of an actor but is shaped by the dynamics of the system in which they operate. Consequently, agency is a **collective capacity** that can be attributed to both individuals, groups or networks within a system. Further, agency needs to be understood across **multiple temporal dimensions**, as past practices created structures and experiences that shape the today's opportunities in the same way as expectations of future opportunities will guide human actions (Kok et al., 2021; Miörner, 2022; Philipp & Amanatidis, 2024). However, the ability to act depends on reflexive utilisation of various knowledge stocks, accessible relations and resources as well as favourable regional conditions and beneficial institutional contexts (Suitner et al., 2022).

In a social innovation context, agency is distinctly highlighting the active role of individuals and groups in driving change, rather than portraying them as passive recipients of technology or policy. It centres on deliberate action, reflecting **actors' capacity to make choices and take initiatives to address social challenges**. This purposeful agency can lead to transformative change, when solutions tailored to the specific needs of communities and shaped by the socio-technical contexts in which they operate, change the context for social practices in a given local context (Philipp & Amanatidis, 2024; Suitner et al., 2022). In this process, actors leverage local resources, knowledge, and networks, often drawing on tacit, context-specific understanding, which enhances the effectiveness of their initiatives (Suitner et al., 2022). **Reflexivity and learning are central** to this individual or collective process, as actors adapt strategies based on past experiences and evolving circumstances. Thus, agency is crucial to social innovation, emphasising human initiative, collaboration, and local contexts in fostering sustainable change, particularly in addressing societal challenges.

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While often perceived and described as initiatives emerging from civil society groups, social enterprises, and grassroots movements, **social innovation actors include actors from all quadruple helices** (Carayannis & Campbell, 2009). This diversity of actors and their interactions, centred on learning and knowledge creation within specific contexts, defines social innovation ecosystems. However, some actors, such as consumers or communities, may experience the distributed agency, making collective action, resource pooling, and scaling more challenging, as a barrier (Terstriep et al., 2015). A perspective on social innovation can be enriched by an ecosystem perspective that integrates these multi-actor, multi-level governance frameworks and highlights the networked, co-produced agency that characterises innovation nowadays.

Thus, from a governance perspective the main question is how to empower the diverse groups of actors engaged in initiatives with transformative potentials so they can effectively use their agency to contribute to processes of social change. **Empowerment and collective agency play a crucial role** in enabling communities and marginalised groups to lead innovation processes that address local climate challenges and drive transformative change. Power, understood as relationally constituted, exists within social contexts and shifts as those contexts evolve, making **power dynamics integral to social innovation and change** (Avelino, 2021). However, the relationship between social innovation and power is complex, as it can challenge and transform existing social structures, but it can also reinforce or create new power imbalances.

Empowerment through social innovation occurs when individuals and communities gain **new ways of organising, acting, and producing knowledge**, which can lead to the co-creation of new social relations (Haxeltine et al., 2016). This increased agency enables social entrepreneurs, activists, and citizens to influence societal change, making empowerment not just a condition for innovation but a core ambition. However, social innovation is not without risks and may show some dark sides if the promotion of self-reliance through innovation serves as a justification for reducing public services and cutting budgets, ultimately disempowering communities by limiting their access to resources and support (Pel et al., 2023).

Moreover, social innovation ecosystems do not empower all actors equally. Certain actors are empowered through the introduction of new social relations, while others may be disempowered, which is essential for systemic change. **Disempowerment of those engaged in harmful practices**, particularly related to environmental degradation, is a key aspect of achieving transformation (Avelino et al., 2019). Specific types of social innovation ecosystems can better facilitate empowerment, supporting the redistribution of agency within the innovation process (Pel et al., . Therefore, empowerment and disempowerment are both critical to understanding how social innovation can lead to meaningful, transformative change.

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2.3.5 Transformative social innovation

Building on the understanding of social innovation outlined above, which focuses on altering social relations to better address societal needs, Pel and colleagues (2020) introduced transformative social innovation as a specific type of social innovation that not only addresses these needs but **also actively challenges, alters, or replaces dominant institutions**. Institutions are defined as formal and informal structures, rules, norms, and practices that shape social, political, and economic behaviour within a society. They represent the "*rules of the game*" that govern individual and collective actions and provide stability and order to social interactions (Battilana et al., 2009; Tolbert & Zucker, 1999). Thus, transformative social innovation seeks to create profound societal change, targeting systemic transformations rather than incremental improvements. In this understanding, transformative social innovation is particularly concerned with reshaping institutional frameworks and power structures to achieve deeper change.

Following (Pel et al., 2020), transformative social innovation builds on a relational framework with several key elements. First, transformative social innovation involves altering social relations, reflecting new ways of doing, knowing, framing, and organising within specific contexts. Additionally, it is based **on four key sets of relations**: i) among actors in social innovation initiatives, ii) between these initiatives and broader networks, iii) between social innovation and institutional change, and iv) between social innovation and the socio-material context in which it operates (see Fig. 2).

First, the **relations within social innovation initiatives** focus on how members collaborate to develop empowering collectives, fostering a sense of community and shared purpose. As examples for this process serve community-based adaptation projects that, through workshops and participatory planning sessions, create new social relations fostering a sense of community and shared purpose among the members. They empower participants by involving them in experimentation, decision-making processes, and enhancing local resilience.

Second, **relations in network formation** highlight the importance of building broader networks that connect various initiatives, facilitating knowledge exchange and resource sharing. The EU's Climate Adaptation Mission could be used as an example of such network formation processes as it connects various stakeholders, including governments, NGOs, and communities, across different regions within an alliance under a shared narrative. The mission facilitates knowledge exchange on best practices for climate adaptation and provides resources to implement successful adaptation strategies. By sharing experiences and information, members of translocal networks can learn from each other, leading to more effective and innovative approaches to climate adaptation in diverse contexts.

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Figure 2: Four sets of relations in transformative social innovation (Pel et al., 2020)

Third, the **relations between social innovation and institutional change** examine how social innovation initiatives interact with and influence existing institutional frameworks, aiming to challenge and transform dominant norms and practices. For example, grassroots movements advocating for climate justice can transpose their logic on local governments to incorporate climate adaptation strategies into urban planning regulations. Another example could be the Covenant of Mayors, where

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local and regional authorities voluntarily commit to increasing energy efficiency and the use of renewable energy sources on their territories and create sustainable energy action plans to this end. Through these institutional changes, social innovation initiatives establish a stable and supportive institutional framework that provides them with access to the necessary resources, legitimacy, and recognition to operate effectively.

Last and fourth, the **relations between social innovation and the socio-material context** consider how the specific environmental, cultural, and economic conditions shape and are shaped by social innovation efforts. This emphasises that social innovations do not exist in isolation but rather are deeply influenced by and interact with path-dependent historical, cultural, economic, and environmental factors present in their specific contexts and as such the outcomes of social-innovation processes might lead to diverse transformations. Together, these interlinked relations provide a comprehensive understanding of how transformative social innovation can emerge and operate within complex social systems.

With this relational focus, transformative social innovation moves beyond merely spreading new practices and knowledge and provides a rationale to understand how its elements help **challenging entrenched institutions and reshape societal structures**. The focus on the interplay of relationships and distributed agency makes transformative social innovation a systemic approach to innovation that builds on changes in practices, governance, meanings, and knowledge, all aimed at transforming institutions and addressing complex social challenges. Castro-Arce and Vanclay (2020) showed that the combination of transformative social innovation and bottom-linked governance, as collaborative "middle ground" where actors from different political levels, sectors, and scales share decision-making power, can contribute to sustainable regional development by connecting local, bottom-up initiatives with broader governance structures. This, further, highlights the importance of bridging institutions and roles (e.g., knowledge brokers, network enablers, resource brokers), which help diverse actors collaborate and to scale up local innovations to achieve broader societal impact.

In essence, **transformative social innovation offers a systemic approach to addressing complex societal challenges** like climate change by reshaping socio-technical systems, fostering new social relations, and promoting inclusive governance. It emphasises the interplay of technological and social innovations, the role of diverse actors and networks, and the importance of shifting institutional structures to create sustainable and resilient solutions. By enabling collaborative efforts and empowering marginalised groups, transformative social innovation holds the potential to drive profound societal change, transitioning from reactive adaptations to proactive, equitable, and sustainable futures.

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2.4 Fostering local and regional adaptation

To apply a transformative social innovation perspective in the context of local adaptation it should be used to foster the integration of innovative solutions, cross-sectoral collaboration, and long-term resilience planning. Crucial to emphasise once again is that local actors - including local and regional governments, businesses, and civil society organisations - are on the front lines of climate impacts and possess unique insights into their specific vulnerabilities and needs. By encouraging them to develop and implement transformative adaptation solutions with the help of transformative framework, local knowledge and creativity can be leveraged to address climate challenges in ways that are both contextually relevant and highly effective.

2.4.1 Transformative knowledge and learning across scales

Innovations developed in one context, whether technological, social, or policy-driven, can **inspire and accelerate adaptation efforts elsewhere**. This kind of learning across scales is crucial for fostering transformative climate adaptation strategies (Juschten et al., 2021). By leveraging knowledge networks, cross-regional as well as cross-sectoral collaborations, local solutions can be adapted to different environments, facilitating a flow of ideas that transcend geographic, sectoral and institutional boundaries (Chu et al., 2017). This circulation of innovative practices allows regions facing similar climate challenges to replicate proven strategies, while saving time and resources and enhancing the overall effectiveness of adaptation efforts (Massey et al., 2014). In this process, policy transfer can play an enabling role in scaling these innovations across regions. When adaptation strategies are successfully **transferred from one context to another**, they can catalyse widespread transformative change, fostering resilience on multiple levels (Schoenefeld et al., 2022). This requires not only the replication of successful models but also a careful consideration of local conditions, ensuring that policies are contextually relevant.

These learning approaches can also play a role in the **translation of theoretical research into practical, actionable strategies** (Storbjörk, 2010). This translation process is often hindered by communication challenges in the collaboration between researchers, policymakers, and practitioners. This transformative knowledge entails knowledge on how to shape and implement the transition from the existing to an envisioned future situation and depends on competences to develop effective policies and to apply strategies such as participation, empowerment, education, and communication (Urmetzer et al., 2020). Adaptation experts often point out the fact that these processes and consequences for adaptation policy are not well understood and that in many cases we are only **at the start of finding practices for good governance** in climate adaptation (Chaffin et al., 2014). Social innovation approaches focus on bridging these gaps by fostering inclusive, multi-stakeholder engagement and designing adaptive solutions tailored to the unique needs of

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communities. Through coordinated knowledge-sharing and collaborative networks, regions can continuously learn from one another, enabling adaptation that is both dynamic and responsive to evolving climate risks (Kalafatis et al., 2015).

2.4.2 Co-production of knowledge and participatory governance

Co-production and collaborative approaches in the design of adaptation strategies are essential for ensuring that climate adaptation is both effective and equitable. Engaging diverse stakeholders, including local scientists, communities, industries, and governments provides a comprehensive understanding of specific climate impacts and vulnerabilities. This is especially true, as **local actors are often on the front lines, offering unique insights into their needs and conditions** (Wamsler & Brink, 2014). This can help in developing contextually relevant solutions (Ross et al., 2015). Furthermore, prioritising the participation of vulnerable and marginalised populations ensures that adaptation strategies do not exacerbate existing inequalities, while promoting **equitable access to technologies used for adaptation efforts**. By integrating local knowledge and creativity, collaborative efforts can result in transformative solutions that are both inclusive and responsive to the varied challenges posed by climate change.

An important concept in this context is **participatory governance**. It can be used to ensure that developed strategies are informed by the experiences, needs, and priorities of those most affected by climate impacts. Doing so, the flexibility and inclusiveness of these communities can be enhanced, making them more resilient and viable in the face of contemporary challenges. Social innovation approaches can be used in such participatory governance efforts by **driving creative, community-led work that responds to complex, local climate challenges**. This also helps to foster greater awareness and understanding of climate issues, leading to stronger community support and collaboration in implementing adaptation measures. Thus, it enhances the **legitimacy and accountability of policies**, whereas the diverse perspectives can lead to more equitable and effective solutions (Uittenbroek et al., 2019).

2.4.3 Just transition and equity in adaptation

The evolving landscape of climate change is reshaping the risks faced by individuals and households, potentially leading to far-reaching socioeconomic repercussions such as heightened poverty, increased inequality, and social unrest (Buhaug et al., 2023). Studies have shown that climate impacts **disproportionately affect vulnerable populations**, such as low-income communities, indigenous peoples, and marginalised groups (O'Brien et al., 2004). These populations often have fewer resources to help them cope with climate shocks. On top of that, they often live in higher-risk areas, and face pre-existing social and economic inequalities that amplify the effects of

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climate change. Without prioritising equity, adaptation efforts risk deepening these disparities, leaving the most affected groups even more exposed (O'Brien & Wolf, 2010). Addressing these unequal vulnerabilities ensures that adaptation efforts are more fair, effective, and prevent the exacerbation of existing injustices.

In the face of this, **social justice** has been an important point of deliberation in contemporary thought on climate adaptation (Newell et al., 2021). Climate adaptation efforts should prioritise equitable access to technology, ensuring that vulnerable and marginalised communities are not left behind (Byskov et al., 2021). As a result, the notion of 'just adaptation' is discussed and implemented in many different domains, from urban planning to social justice theory, to economics to policy implementation and so on. These kinds of perspectives draw attention to adaptation options and their implementation processes, shedding light on the dynamics that can produce winners, losers, and inevitable trade-offs (Schlosberg et al., 2017).

Achieving just adaptation to climate change involves several key strategies. First, **participatory strategies** that have already been mentioned before can also benefit just adaptation. When they include a particular emphasis on the active involvement of marginalised communities, they can aid the adoption of inclusive values and practices. Furthermore, also knowledge co-production strategies can be deployed to integrate local and indigenous knowledge with scientific expertise to ensure culturally relevant solutions. Second, **equitable resource distribution** focuses on prioritising vulnerable groups in the allocation of funding, technology, and support systems, minimising the burden of adaptation costs on disadvantaged populations. In many cases, this involves a redefinition of existing social protection in a way that it becomes strategically positioned to contribute to resilient adaptation (Costella et al., 2023). Third, **capacity-building efforts** can help by targeting empowerment through education, training, and infrastructure development, enabling communities to adapt autonomously while ensuring an inclusive approach. Finally, a **sensible configuration of adaptation technologies** can support the just adaptation process. Components of just transition can be addressed in for instance risk mapping, resilience building, and development of responses to extreme climate events.

Social innovation can be seen as a powerful framework for establishing and guiding a just transition approach. It has core focus on empowering communities to address social challenges through creative and sustainable solutions, which aligns well with just transition values and practices. In short, social innovation frameworks strongly emphasise local participation, while fostering grassroots initiatives that are **attuned to the specific needs and contexts** of the community. By encouraging collaboration and co-creation, social innovation approaches aim to harness the collective intelligence and resources of communities, leading to more resilient and adaptable outcomes. Additionally, it promotes social equity and inclusion by giving marginalised groups a voice in the development

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process, ensuring that solutions are more equitable and widely beneficial. Ultimately, the goal of the social innovation framework is to facilitate meaningful and enduring change by leveraging the strengths and insights of those directly impacted by social issues.

2.4.4 Narratives of transformative change and local futures

Aligning long-term adaptation strategies with how people experience current climate conditions remains a challenge. Even if the topic of climate change is becoming more prominent in people's daily lives, the problem of psychological distance is widely reported when it comes to acting on climate change (Keller et al., 2022; Maiella et al., 2020). Furthermore, akin to the predicaments presented by climate change, the broader discussion on climate change and adaptation is often dominated by a **doom and gloom narrative** (Hinkel et al., 2020). This is problematic because to foster public support and collaboration, adaptation efforts must **resonate with local concerns and aspirations**. Therefore, it is important to address these issues in the development and implementation of adaptation measures.

The construction of **engaging narratives can be used to motivate** different kinds of adaptive climate action, as they help in empowering and unifying people around recognisable visions for solutions (Moezzi et al., 2017). The topic of climate adaptation is generally so multifaceted and complex that these kinds of narratives can play a role in the development of and support for actionable plans (Paschen & Ison, 2014). In such a context, narratives of change offer a way to explore how citizens perceive past, present, and future weather and climate patterns and their connection to envisioned future outcomes (Marschütz et al., 2020). The different kinds of imaginaries can help shape regional stakeholder's perceptions and **empower actors in taking advantage of opportunities** (Wittmayer et al., 2019). Furthermore, while the perception of opportunities and the capabilities to realise these opportunities vary between actors and regions, it is important to understand how the regional narratives can be translated into a more widespread vision and contribute to an effective multi-level framework for the global goal on adaptation.

2.5 Barriers and enablers of transformative adaptation

Recognising the essential role of local and regional governments in climate adaptation, it is crucial to explore the barriers and enablers that influence transformative adaptation efforts. Without addressing these challenges, adaptation initiatives risk becoming fragmented, uncoordinated, and inadequately funded, which can result in inequitable and ineffective responses (Leach et al., 2007). A successful **transformative approach necessitates a cohesive framework of governance** measures that provide the necessary regulations, incentives, and enforcement mechanisms (Smith et al., 2009). These measures are vital for ensuring collective action, fostering compliance, and

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promoting resilient and sustainable practices while supporting vulnerable communities and facilitating stakeholder cooperation. In the following section, we will identify **key obstacles** and **factors that enable** transformative adaptation, synthesising insights from the literature on social innovation and transformative change (Biesbroek et al., 2013).

2.5.1 Barriers

The main barriers to adaptation can be summarised under the points of resource constraints, institutional inertia, and cultural and societal resistances. Regarding resource constraints, especially local governments often grapple with severe gaps that hinder effective climate adaptation. These constraints go beyond just financial limitations, since also technical expertise, human capital, and information (e.g. lack of robust data) play an important role. This risks the **sidelining of local adaptation strategies**, while they become perceived as long-term investments that do not yield visible short-term benefits. Moreover, because of lacking resources, **climate adaptation quickly becomes an afterthought** rather than an integrated part of local governance. This type of structural constraints perpetuates the underfunding and postponement of critical adaptation actions and poses the risk of maladaptation, which can leave local institutions ill-prepared to cope with escalating climate risks.

These resource constraints are often caused by **fragmented governance and limited policy coherence** at local levels. This dilutes the effectiveness of climate strategies, as coordination across sectors is minimal. Part and parcel of this issue is the short-term nature of political horizons. Local policymakers are often pressured to deliver immediate results to maintain political capital, which makes resourceful, long-term anticipatory adaptation measures less politically attractive. Whereas external funding could alleviate some of these constraints, many municipalities are hesitant because of complex application processes, or because they cannot provide required matching local funds. Also, even when funding is available, the absence of local technical capacity to design and implement robust adaptation measures can lead to misallocation or underutilisation of resources.

Further, institutional inertia is a major barrier to effective climate adaptation innovations. It refers to the **tendency of established organisations and systems to resist change**. This is often manifested as reluctance to adopt innovative approaches and necessary reforms, hindering timely responses to emerging climate challenges as local policy makers tend to prioritise risk aversion and routine operations. In the face of increasingly complex environmental issues, this inability of institutions to evolve or adapt can limit the effectiveness of strategies and impede the overall progress toward resilience. Instead, it is likely to result in a status quo that does not adequately address the urgent and dynamic nature of climate risks.

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Institutional inertia is often fuelled by **siload governance structures and entrenched bureaucratic norms**. In many local contexts, agencies still operate in isolation, limiting cross-sector collaboration that is crucial for holistic climate adaptation efforts (Russel et al., 2020). This lack of integration prevents the sharing of critical insights and resources, reinforcing outdated approaches (Den Uyl & Russel, 2018). For instance, climate adaptation responsibilities may be dispersed across various departments or agencies, each operating with its own budgetary and operational limitations. Furthermore, rigid bureaucratic processes, characterised by a **preference for established protocols and a general aversion to risk**, often stifle innovation and discourage the adoption of adaptive strategies. Together, these factors perpetuate reliance on traditional systems, slowing the institution's capacity to respond to evolving climate challenges. The multifaceted nature of climate adaptation, however, where systemic vulnerabilities are hard to categorise, further complicates these matters. The **variability and uncertainty in climate projections**, along with **incomplete and contradictory adaptation requirements** can lead to significant challenges to the formulation of effective adaptation policies (Lemos & Rood, 2010; Siders & Pierce, 2021). This kind of epistemic uncertainty can exacerbate institutional inertia by complicating the development of precise, actionable plans (Sluijs, 2012). This often leads to delays in policy development and insufficient prioritisation of action and allocation of resources.

Further, **resistance to climate change adaptation**, rooted in cultural or societal concerns slows the implementation of effective climate adaptation strategies. Especially, in situations where not only appropriate solutions but also the problem definition is contested (Wanzenböck et al., 2020). The resulting divergence of perspectives between different stakeholders and the need to balance these competing demands can lead to societal pushback or reluctance to embrace necessary changes. This barrier makes it challenging to build the necessary public support for transformative adaptation measures and impede proactive and informed decision-making. Furthermore, local climate adaptation efforts often require coordination across sectors, levels of government, and diverse stakeholder groups. The resistance caused by cultural and societal fragmentation ultimately undermines efforts to adapt to climate change, even when this is vital for a community's long-term resilience.

Looking into common causes for cultural or societal barriers, **communities often resist changes that challenge deeply rooted social norms, traditions, or ways of life** (Brink et al., 2023). Adaptation measures may be viewed as disruptive to local identities, livelihoods, or cultural practices, particularly in regions where climate policies impose new regulations on resource use or land management. Also, climate adaptation efforts can clash with political ideologies or be seen as catering to elite interests and be perceived as a threat to autonomy or an attempt of economic displacement. These issues further fuel scepticism and slowing the adoption of necessary reforms.

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Further, **reduced public confidence in the efficacy of adaptation measures** undermines both political will and community engagement, stalling implementation. Scepticism may arise from perceived slow progress, lack of tangible benefits, or distrust in institutions, leading to disengagement and resistance. General climate change scepticism further aggravates this issue, as it weakens public belief in the necessity of adaptation measures altogether. This creates a feedback loop where the lack of visible success fuels further doubt, hindering efforts to scale up effective adaptation strategies.

2.5.2 Enablers

As outlined above, transformative change and transformative adaptation hold the promise of systemic shifts toward resilience and sustainability but are also fraught with potential risks and failures. Thus, effective transformation requires not only breaking systemic lock-ins (Geels, 2024) but the deliberate fostering of **enabling conditions to achieve meaningful, long-term outcomes**. Key enablers of transformative adaptation include engaging leaders and key actors, reflexive learning, ongoing investments in research and experimentation, the development of partnerships and networks across different governance levels and scales, multi-stakeholder engagement, as well as institutional support (Fedele et al., 2019a). By addressing these factors, regions can navigate the complex pathways of adaptation while building systems that are both, resilient to future climate impacts and equitable in their distribution of benefits.

Generally, transformative innovation policies aim at mitigating transformative failures (Weber & Rohracher, 2012) and enabling transformative outcomes (Ghosh et al., 2021) as a basis for transformative change. In climate adaptation this entails addressing systemic challenges while leveraging key enablers that support transformative change. To avoid transformation system failures the following aspects are crucial. **Transformation requires a certain directionality** that actors can follow, thus it is important to develop coherent policies that align with long-term transformative goals and establish shared visions of the future. This is aligned with the need to engage the key actors in processes of **demand articulation** and joint learning processes, such as living labs and strategic niche management (Raven et al., 2010), to ensure that innovation is responsive to the needs of envisioned adaptation pathways.

Effective **policy coordination is vital for preventing fragmented efforts**. Aligning national, regional, and sectoral policies and improving coordination mechanisms across governance levels ensures that transformation is implemented in a systematic way. In this context, the OECD (2015) speaks of a *whole-of-government approach*, which builds on identifying and tackling the most urgent contradiction and trade-offs between strategic objectives and policies. Related to this identification, the creation of **reflexive governance structures** that allow continuous monitoring and collective

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sensemaking is important to re-evaluate development trajectories, and open new adaptation pathways, especially in response to extreme climate events or political reforms.

Building on the multi-level understanding of transformative innovation policy, Gosh and colleagues (2021) introduced transformative outcomes as an intermediate policy objective level. Following this thinking, transformative change processes can be supported by building and nurturing niches, expanding and mainstreaming niches, and unlocking and opening-up regimes. **Building and nurturing niches** involves creating supportive environments where innovative practices can develop and thrive. This process is crucial for enabling transformations as it allows for the emergence of alternative practices that eventually can replace existing systems. These processes involve shielding niche innovations from external pressures and competition, allowing them to grow without being immediately undermined by established regimes, networking, knowledge exchange, and shared learning among niche actors to enhance their capabilities and innovation processes. This broadening and deepening of networks is essential for increasing the transformative potential of niches by incorporating various perspectives and reducing the risk of social exclusion. Lastly, managing the expectations of different niche stakeholders can help align interests and foster collaboration.

Expanding and mainstreaming niches involves the process of increasing the size and influence of innovative practices so that they can be generalised in broader societal systems. This is essential for ensuring that successful innovations move beyond their initial contexts and gain wider acceptance and credibility. This involves processes of upscaling, which refers to the increased adoption of new systems by users, replication, which focuses on intentionally facilitating the replication of successful niche experiments in different contexts, circulation, which promotes the spreading of ideas, people, or technologies between niches, and institutionalising, which entails the mainstreaming of rules, behaviour, beliefs, and values, of the niche among existing and new niche actors. Overall, expanding and mainstreaming niches is about ensuring that innovative ideas and practices gain traction and become part of the mainstream, thereby contributing to larger transformation processes within society

The process, of **unlocking and opening-up regimes** involves addressing and transforming the existing structures and practices that hinder the adoption of innovative solutions. This is crucial for creating opportunities for niche innovations to expand and gain traction within established systems. As part of this process, it is important to destabilise existing regime rules that support incremental changes and maintain the status quo. This involves challenging the rigidity of established practices and beliefs that can obstruct the integration of new ideas. By creating a sense of urgency or necessity for change, stakeholders can open discussions about alternative approaches. This process entails unlearning and deep learning among regime actors, which mean that they must be willing to let go

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of outdated practices and embrace new knowledge that can facilitate transformation. **Strengthening interactions between regimes and niches** is also essential, as it fosters collaboration and knowledge exchange that can lead to more innovative solutions. Finally, changing perceptions of landscape pressures is important for unlocking regimes. This involves reframing how stakeholders view external challenges, such as environmental issues or social inequalities, to encourage a more proactive response to these pressures. By shifting perspectives, regimes can become more receptive to transformative innovations. Overall, unlocking and opening up regimes is about creating the necessary conditions for niche innovations to flourish by challenging existing norms and fostering a more dynamic and adaptable system.

In conclusion, **addressing the barriers and leveraging enablers for transformative climate adaptation** is critical to overcoming systemic challenges and fostering long-term resilience. Resource constraints, institutional inertia, and cultural resistance are significant obstacles, often rooted in fragmented governance, bureaucratic silos, and societal reluctance to change. These barriers impede the implementation of innovative and anticipatory adaptation strategies, undermining efforts to build resilience to escalating climate risks. However, key enablers, such as engaging key actors, fostering multi-stakeholder collaborations, investing in research, and creating reflexive governance structures, provide pathways for overcoming these challenges. By nurturing niches of innovation, expanding and mainstreaming successful practices, and unlocking rigid regimes, transformative outcomes can be achieved. These strategies not only facilitate systemic shifts towards sustainability but also ensure that adaptation efforts are inclusive, responsive to local needs, and resilient in the face of future climate uncertainties. Ultimately, navigating the interplay of barriers and enablers is essential for fostering adaptive capacities and ensuring the successful implementation of transformative climate adaptation.

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3 Defining regional strategies: Methodology of the report

Based on the theoretical understanding, we developed a relational approach for transformative social innovation in climate adaptation. This approach introduces four key focus areas, that can support the uptake of innovative solutions and embed transformative practices in existing societal systems. The following section on the approach discusses these key focus areas and operationalises them through specific objectives and strategic actions to support the development of a supportive environment for socially innovative transformative adaptation. Building on these theoretical understanding, we collected regional data through interviews and co-creation workshops, as basis for supporting the regional LSD teams and governance systems in their adaptation efforts. The methodological approach for these interviews and workshops will be explained in the second section.

3.1 Approach: A relational approach for the LSDs

Building on the theoretical context outlined in the previous sections, we frame socially innovative climate adaptation as both incremental and transformative actions, focusing on resilience, equity, and justice to reduce vulnerabilities and enhance adaptive capacities. Central to that understanding is that innovation and adaptation are more than technological change and require changes in social spheres and relations. Consequently, we build on the transformative social innovation framework to maximise the impact of the regional Large-Scale Demonstrator work implemented in RESIST. TSI **emphasises collective empowerment, network formation, and institutional change to challenge entrenched norms and practices, creating systemic change through participatory and inclusive approaches.** The thinking informing this report, is further shaped by socio-technical transitions frameworks, highlighting the dynamics between niches, regimes, and landscapes. These levels and dynamics between them explain how innovative practices emerge, mature, and disrupt stable systems under external pressures. Together, these theoretical approaches underline the importance of fostering governance flexibility, experimentation, participatory networks, and collaborative learning to align local innovations with systemic goals, enabling sustainable and equitable transformations in response to climate and societal risks.

Generally, climate change adaptation requires a rethinking of the socio-ecological organisation of our societies. The plurality of climate hazards and vulnerabilities requires place-based solutions that respond to local contingencies and requirements shaped by local institutional arrangements. Adaptation, thus, depends on the development and implementation of context-specific solutions that

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align with the interests of local actors, which are created within a new policy setting across all levels and sectoral departments of public administrations. **These change-oriented governance practices can be described as social innovation as they aim to increase resilience, equity, and justice.** The approaches depend on coordinating transformation processes with a directionality towards climate-resilient regional development within and across European territories (Castro-Arce & Vanclay, 2020; Weber et al., 2024).

As such, climate change adaptation is an **emergent bricolage of practices** in governance, industry, markets, science, culture, and technology (Hölsgens et al., 2018) that aims to enable transformative regional development. As local demands and adaptation solutions might not be clear from the beginning, such processes require a governance paradigm depending on experimentation and a reconfiguration of local assets (Kuhlmann et al., 2019; Weber & Rohracher, 2012), which in turn builds upon inclusion of actors with specialised and localised knowledge as well as bottom-linked governance.

In RESIST, such an understanding entails that we see **social innovation as a cultural change in the governance practices** on the regime level, that supports the transformation processes within the LSDs, which are experimentations on the niche level. These two levels cannot be separated as the governance of transformation processes depends on experimental processes that create changes in knowledge, attitudes, skills and aspirations (Castro-Arce & Vanclay, 2020; Kuhlmann et al., 2019). This is an **ongoing process that started before RESIST and will not be finished with the project's end.** Thus, the social innovation in the LSD regions is not contingent on RESIST but the project provides a window of opportunity to further institutionalise the process. To support this process, we elaborate a relational framework for the RESIST transformative social innovation strategies following the four sets of relations as identified by Pel and colleagues (2020). As this framework rests on the integration of the theoretical understandings of climate change adaptation and transformative adaptation, transformative social innovation, and other enabling frameworks for regional adaptation, **we label these sets of relations as key focus areas** to distinct them from their original theoretical understanding.

3.1.1 Relations in the SI initiatives

Relations within the LSDs address the collaborative dynamics among RESIST partners with the aim to foster empowerment and a shared directionality. TSI-informed strategies require to highlight the importance of localised efforts to address societal challenges through innovative practices. Such an initiative needs to enable collective responses to unmet social needs, which are characterised by creativity, resource pooling, and participatory governance.

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The main concepts for this key focus area are **agency and empowerment** as fundamental elements to understanding the relations within the LSDs. Agency reflects the capacity of individuals and groups to actively reshape societal structures through intentional action (Grillitsch & Sotarauta, 2020; Suitner et al., 2022). It includes interpersonal relations and organisational forms within social innovation initiatives. Empowerment enables participants to co-create solutions, particularly in climate adaptation, where the ability to act depends on access to actors, resources and reflexive use of resources with regional conditions, multi-scalar networks and institutional configurations and critical junctures of events (Avelino, 2021). The emphasis on collaboration ensures a mobilisation of these conditions and the inclusion of diverse voices contributing to problem-solving, creating a sense of ownership and commitment among stakeholders.

The key focus area also considers **learning and reflexivity** within these initiatives. Transformative knowledge processes, including iterative learning and the co-production of knowledge, foster adaptability (Urmetzer et al., 2020; Weber & Rohrer, 2012). By integrating local knowledge with scientific insights, LSD teams address context-specific challenges while building capacity for future resilience (Borrás et al., 2023). Additionally, fostering new social relations enhances trust, mutual understanding, and collective action. These **internal dynamics create a foundation for scaling and replicating**, as well as for future development of successful innovations (Weber et al., 2024). They enable initiatives to become hubs of experimentation and innovation, generating insights that inform broader systemic changes. Ultimately, relations within the LSDs embody the collaborative spirit and bottom-up approaches essential for transformative social change.

To **operationalise** this reasoning in the context of RESIST, we developed a specific objective and three strategic actions for the Key Focus Area 1: Dynamics within the LSDs. Generally, the objective is to strengthen and maintain collaborative dynamics within LSDs teams as a mechanism for fostering sustainable empowerment and shared directionality. TSI strategies need to enable collective, context-specific responses to transformative climate adaptation, depending on agency, empowerment, and reflexive learning. This can be achieved through the establishment of an **adaptation platform**, as a sustainable organisational entity, bringing together key stakeholders for regional adaptation processes. Such a platform is temporarily established or seeded through the LSD teams and their core stakeholders through the RESIST project, but as most adaptation processes will go beyond the project's lifetime, the development of a sustainable structure can support the creating of long-term impacts. To effectively drive change beyond the project, the strategic establishment of collective **transformative capacities** and safeguarding **reflexive learning** and governance are further key elements, which are tied to a sustainable structure, providing an arena for exchange and initiation of further adaptation initiatives.

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3.1.2 Relation in network formation

Network formation refers to the connections and collaborations that link LSDs and regional and translocal stakeholders. Following the TSI thinking, networks facilitate knowledge exchange, resource sharing, and coordinated action, enabling innovations to transcend local contexts and contribute to systemic transformation when embedded in different communities and contexts.

The key concepts to understand network formation are the role of **collaborative governance and multi-level coordination** in cultivating effective networks (Ansell & Gash, 2008; Massuga et al., 2024). Participatory governance and cross-sectoral collaboration are pivotal in forming networks that bridge gaps between local actors, policymakers, and international frameworks, like e.g., the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change. These networks amplify the impact of the LSDs by creating platforms for dialogue and shared learning. Empowerment and inclusivity are equally relevant in this context. Networks must accommodate diverse perspectives, ensuring that unusual actors and local communities are actively involved. Collaborative networks create spaces for stakeholders to co-create solutions, aligning local priorities with broader adaptation and innovation goals. This inclusivity strengthens the legitimacy and accountability of network activities. While translocal networks provide the basis for the circulation of ideas and replication of solutions in different contexts.

To facilitate the development of networks, narratives play a critical role. Engaging **narratives help to unify diverse stakeholders around shared objectives** (Hinkel et al., 2020; Wittmayer et al., 2019), creating a sense of purpose and direction. By highlighting the successes and challenges of individual initiatives, networks inspire collective action and encourage the replication of effective practices across regions and sectors. Ultimately, relations in network formation illustrate the importance of interconnectedness in scaling the results of the LSD processes. Networks act as conduits for transformative ideas, enabling the flow of resources, knowledge, and support that are necessary to achieve systemic change.

We **operationalise the network formation** through a specific objective and three strategic actions as the Key Focus Area 2: Network formation beyond the LSDs. Generally, these actions aim to strategically expand the regional and international networks to enable the collaborative governance, inclusivity, and multi-level coordination. The creation of inclusive narratives of adaptation is central to unify stakeholders around shared objectives and encouraging replication across regions and sectors. **Networks** can be developed and be beneficial for these efforts both, regionally, as well as internationally and include stakeholders, peers, as well as users, supporting the **diffusion of the solutions**. Gathering these actors under a shared **narrative** supports the developing a shared development direction.

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3.1.3 Relations to institutional change

Relations towards institutional change focus on how LSDs interact with and influence existing frameworks to challenge entrenched norms, rules, and practices. Following TSI thinking, institutional change is pivotal for scaling and sustaining transformative innovations (Schot & Steinmueller, 2018; Tolbert & Zucker, 1999). Thus, for LSDs to successfully engage in a transformative adaptation process, it is central to understand dominant societal rulesets as well as the way more radical alternatives can fit into and transform existing structures.

The third key focus area highlights the **importance of systemic lock-ins that resist change** and the need to challenge and replace commonly accepted approaches as a basis for transformation (Fazey et al., 2016; Kivimaa & Kern, 2016). Members of the LSD teams need to collaborate with and empower actors that challenge rigid institutional structures and contribute to these processes themselves by proposing alternative governance models, policy reforms, and participatory frameworks. These efforts seek to dismantle existing power imbalances and establish more equitable systems. The institutional change thinking stresses that emerging transformative adaptation approaches often build upon new logics (Thornton & Ocasio, 2008), which challenge existing ways of governance. To support a systemic change, the niche logics that are supported by the LSD initiatives, must be generalised from the experimental niches to existing regimes. By strategically interacting with regimes and responding to landscape pressures, the LSDs can carefully construct critical junctures that allow for influence on policy changes, governance reforms, and resource allocation.

At the core, members of the LSD teams strive to **identify, challenge, and renegotiate** the frameworks, cognitive models, identities, roles, and arrangements that enable unsustainable behaviours and routines through innovative alternative practices. While this is a long-term process, the empowerment of actors and showcasing of alternatives through the regional pilots can support advocacy for policy shifts that align with transformative adaptation goals. These efforts require reflexive governance structures that promote continuous adaptation and learning. This approach towards institutional change underscores the transformative potential of social innovation. By reshaping institutional frameworks, LSDs contribute to conditions for broader systemic change, ensuring that innovations are not merely experimental but integral to long-term sustainability.

We **operationalise the relations to institutional change** through one specific objective and three strategic actions as the Key Focus Area 3: Catalysing institutional change through the LSD. The specific objective of this Key Focus Area is to influence institutional change by challenging entrenched norms and structures, promoting alternative governance models, as foundation of facilitating transformative adaptation processes. Addressing systemic lock-ins is key to support

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broader change and sustainable development in the long term. These relates to the actions of **challenging unsustainable practices**, and **institutionalisation of adaptation efforts**, and a conscious identification and articulation of **new logics** that the RESIST solutions hold and how their implementation in governance and diffusion contexts can be supported.

3.1.4 Relations to the socio-material context

The key focus area stresses the relationship of social innovation with its socio-material context and the interactions with its environmental, cultural, and economic surroundings. These relations emphasise the embeddedness of initiatives within specific contexts and their influence on broader systemic transformations.

The key focus area introduces concepts like **resilience, adaptive capacity, and vulnerability**, which are integral to understanding the socio-material dimension (Pelling, 2010; Smit & Wandel, 2006). The LSDs and their actions emerged as response to specific climate challenges rooted in the specific regional context. These initiatives leverage local knowledge, cultural practices, and ecological systems to develop contextually relevant solutions. This interplay between social and material factors highlights the importance of systems thinking. By addressing vulnerabilities within socio-ecological systems, the LSDs contribute to resilience-building and sustainability. The implementation of solutions requires certain adaptive pathways and the navigation of uncertainties that are rooted in these local socio-material contexts.

Path-dependended infrastructures, policy approaches, cultural and societal resistance shape established practices and their relations to the socio-material context (Boschma et al., 2017; Martin & Sunley, 2006). Thus, innovations must navigate entrenched norms and scepticism, aligning their practices with local values and aspirations. Ultimately, relations in the socio-material context illustrate **the interconnectedness of social innovations and their environments**. These interactions shape the outcomes of initiatives, influencing their scalability, sustainability, and transformative impact (Weber et al., 2024). By addressing socio-material challenges holistically, social innovations contribute to systemic resilience and equitable development.

These relations are **operationalised** in the Key Focus Area 4: Shaping the socio-material context, that consists of one specific objective and two strategic actions. The objective relates to the need to examine the interplay between transformative adaptation efforts and their socio-material context as a basis for navigating path-dependent infrastructures and socio-ecological vulnerabilities. Fostering resilience and adaptive capacities will ultimately depend on a successful transformation of the material configuration of regional societies. The strategic actions in this regard relate to the actual

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transformation of the socio-material context and the identification and development of approaches to overcome **path-dependencies**, that might block adaptation efforts.

3.2 Methodology

3.2.1 Interviews

Interviews offer vital, context-specific insights that enhance climate adaptation strategies by capturing in-depth qualitative data about the experiences, perceptions, and local knowledge of project partners. They help tailor transformative adaptation efforts to specific contexts, ensuring strategies are relevant, effective, and equitable. Additionally, interviews can be used to support participatory engagement, building trust with partners and stakeholders, while uncovering adaptive behaviours already in place. This firsthand knowledge is also crucial for understanding the complex social dimensions of the respective region's climate impacts and adaptation effectiveness. Furthermore, interviews also serve as a tool for evaluating adaptation strategies over time, offering feedback on successes and challenges, enabling continuous improvement. Finally, they help capture local/regional narratives that reflect the specific experiences with climate change, providing unique insights into adaptation practices. Thus, by emphasising the human element, interviews help fostering targeted responses that are both effective and informed by on-the-ground experiences.

The interviews were conducted during the summer and fall of 2023, across all four RESIST LSD regions with a total of 26 interviewees.

Southwest Finland

- The Regional Council of Southwest Finland (1 interviewee)
- City of Turku (1 interviewee)
- University of Turku (1 interviewee)
- Natural Resources Institute Finland (1 interviewee)
- Turku University of Applied Sciences (1 interviewee)

Central Denmark

- Region Midtjylland (1 interviewee)
- NIRAS (1 interviewee)
- Coastal Authority (2 interviewees)
- VIA University (1 interviewee)
- Aarhus University (1 interviewee)

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Catalonia

- Polytechnic University of Catalonia (1 interviewee)
- HYDS (1 interviewee)
- Open University of Catalonia (2 interviewees)
- Municipality of Terrassa (2 interviewees)
- Catalonia Directorate of Civil Protection (1 interviewee)

Central Portugal

- CCDRC (2 interviewees)
- Intermunicipal Community of Coimbra Region (1 interviewee)
- Intermunicipal Community of the Médio Tejo Region (1 interviewee)
- ForestWISE (1 interviewee)
- BLC3 (2 interviewees)
- Polytechnic Institute of Portalegre (1 interviewee)

These interviews were coordinated to ensure a comprehensive understanding of governance practices and the potential for social innovation. The questionnaire covered the regional background, regional adaptation efforts generally and in RESIST specifically, stakeholders, and transformative visions regarding the impact of the LSD. Adhering to the project's ethics guidelines, interviewees received detailed consent forms well in advance of the interviews, allowing them time to review and provide informed consent. The interviews were analysed in structured grids, and the data were triangulated with findings from the Needs Assessment (D1.1) conducted in WP1. This integration strengthened the validity of the results by cross-referencing different data sources. Furthermore, the results were key in the preparation for the co-creation workshops (see below).

3.2.2 Co-creation workshops

Co-creation workshops are based on a collaborative and interactive process that is focused on bringing together a group of individuals to envision the desired processes and outcomes of the under a shared vision. It is meant to create a dynamic and inclusive process that forms a sense of ownership and commitment among LSD participants. As a method, it is often used in community development, strategic planning, and organisational goal setting. In our specific context, we aimed to use it as such, but additionally it also helped to validate and enrich the findings from the interviews that took place in the months before the workshop. The workshop sessions centre around the different RESIST LSDs and encourage participants from the regions to share their perspectives on the current status of their LSD and on issues that need to be addressed.

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The co-creation workshops were coordinated and organised together with all four LSD regions during the summer of 2024. The content and focus of the individual workshops were adapted where needed to meet the respective LSD needs. The invitations to the workshops were managed by the regions, following the suggestion to bring together up to 10 representatives of regional partners and/or important stakeholders that are close to the project implementation. Subsequently, the workshops were attended by 4 to 11 people each with a cumulative total of 28 participants. The workshops' details are as follows:

- The co-creation WS with Catalonia took place on the 27.06.2024, a total of 11 people participated.
- The co-creation WS with Central Denmark took place on the 27.06.2024, a total of 4 people participated.
- The co-creation WS with Central Portugal took place on the 03.07.2024, a total of 7 people participated.
- The co-creation WS with Southwest Finland took place on the 27.08.2024, a total of 6 people participated.

Present LSD partners engaged in brainstorming sessions centred around the four Key Focus Areas elaborated above. This was used to introduce the TSI's ideas and concepts, after which these were discussed in plenary. These discussions helped to nurture feedback, reflection and cross-pollination of ideas among participants. The focus was on synthesising and validating a collective vision from the inputs of individual LSD partners by identifying common themes, values, and priorities that emerged. This provided valuable insights into each of the LSDs' challenges and opportunities.

Participants highlighted the importance of addressing social dimensions, while emphasising strategies to engage policymakers. Discussions also explored the transformative potential of the LSDs, assessing the strengths and weaknesses of their teams and stakeholder networks. Reflexivity emerged as a key area, with participants discussing current learning practices and identifying ways to enhance adaptability. Additionally, the workshops mapped critical actors and local discourses essential for driving change, while also examining institutional barriers and strategies to overcome them within LSD actions.

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4 Transformative social innovation strategy

The following chapter contains the main outcomes of the analysis outlined in the previous chapters. Based on the theoretical approach discussed in chapter three, and the analysis of the regional LSDs and contexts, an approach for a transformative social innovation strategy for transformative climate adaptation has been developed. By integrating theory and the analysis of the regional characteristics, LSDs' foci, and other activities that are envisioned during the RESIST project, it provides a basis to identify measures to maximise the impact of these activities building on a social innovation perspective. The outcome of that process are the building blocks of a transformative social innovation strategy that consist of four key focus areas and eleven strategic actions. By addressing these elements, the framework conditions for transformative climate adaptation measures can be influenced positively. While the single strategies actions might be more or less relevant in a given regional context, the approach provides a lens to identify and priorities actions and to identify blind spots in current transformation strategies. The following section provides a comparative overview of the mobilisation of the methodological approach in the context of RESIST. The second section of this chapter provides outlook and a plan for the implementation work over the next years.

4.1 Contexts and building blocks for regional strategies

Based on the approach and data collected in cooperation with the regional partners (see chapter 3), the following section provides a comparative overview of the regional contexts and approaches in the RESIST project. This section presents the regional contexts and the work they focus on in the context of the RESIST project, but it further illustrates these efforts in the context of the four key focus areas and strategic actions elaborated above. These analysis shows that together with other project activities, most strategic actions are somewhat addressed, however, not all the strategic actions are represented in all the adaptation efforts of all regions. These gabs are particularly interesting for advancing the transformative potential of these approaches.

4.1.1 Regional contexts and solutions

The four LSD regions, Southwest Finland, Central Denmark, Catalonia, and Central Portugal, face distinct climate change vulnerabilities. However, despite their unique geographical, ecological, and socio-economic contexts, all regions experience the intensifying impacts of rising temperatures, altered precipitation patterns, and extreme weather events. As will become clear below, the

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adaptation challenges revolve around governance, ecosystem resilience, and socio-economic equity.

4.1.1.1 Southwest Finland

Southwest Finland is characterised by a mix of urban and rural landscapes, fertile farmlands, and the vulnerable Archipelago Sea. Rising temperatures, increased precipitation, and extreme weather threaten its ecosystems, agriculture, and urban areas. Additionally, the marine ecosystems in the Archipelago Sea face degradation due to nutrient pollution and oxygen depletion through agricultural runoff.

RESIST’s adaptation efforts in Southwest Finland focus on NbS to address water management while enhancing biodiversity and resilience. Floodplains, like to ones connect to the **two-stage ditch**, and wetland restoration are key strategies to mitigate rural flooding, absorb excess water, filter pollutants, and improve water quality. Other efforts in the region focus on **river catchment planning**, balancing ecological health and stakeholder needs. These efforts are validated via new approaches towards **watershed modelling**.

Table 1: Overview of available solutions by South-West Finland (RESIST Deliverable 3.4)

Name of solution	Solution type	Short description
Two-stage ditch	Physical solution	A 2-stage ditch is a NbS that mimics a natural streambed. It consists of a main channel, where water flows when water volume is low, and floodplains, where water has more room to flow in times of increased water volume. Flood plains provide space and water retention capacity. Vegetation in floodplains prevents erosion and removes nutrients from the water.
Blue-green factor	Policy instrument	The Blue Green Factor is a factor-based policy instrument to ensure and maintain desired levels of green and blue in new development projects.
Raingarden catalogue	Information provision approach	The catalogue describes alternatives to create raingardens. Raingarden is a nature-based climate change adaptation measure fit for a residential property.

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River catchment planning	Planning approach	Multi-objective and multi-beneficial catchment-based planning process provides a bottom-up approach and holistic view to water management and stakeholder engagement.
Watershed modelling	Decision making aid and stakeholder engagement tool	SWAT and watershed modelling helps identifying climate risks with climate scenario testing and choosing the right climate change adaptation methods. The model is constructed and validated with spatial and climatic datasets. It shows potential benefits already before implementation to increase acceptance in decision-making and landowners.
Cost-benefit analysis of NbS	Decision making aid	Approach to evaluate the costs and, benefits and efficiency of NbS in economic terms

In urban areas like Turku, **raingardens** green roofs, and permeable pavements are promoted so as to reduce runoff, improve infiltration, and mitigate urban heat islands. Advanced water-treatment systems prevent industrial pollution, while restored wetlands strengthen resilience. Collaboration across municipalities, industries, and communities ensures these measures align with regional sustainability goals. The LSD also aims to demonstrate the cost-effectiveness of such solutions through dedicated **cost-benefit analysis for NbS** tools and, subsequently, support the integration of NbS in land-use and agricultural planning, incl. the **blue-green factor**. The solutions are introduced above and discussed in detail in Deliverable 3.4.

4.1.1.2 Central Denmark

The **Central Denmark** region is distinguished by its extensive coastline and network of water bodies. Its low-lying geography makes it particularly susceptible to rising sea levels and inland flooding. Key urban centres like Randers and Horsens are highly vulnerable to these flooding hazards. These vulnerabilities are compounded by fragmented adaptation efforts.

In RESIST, Central Denmark focuses on fostering resilience to flooding through improved decision-making processes in urban planning and risk management. It combines participatory strategies and advanced tools, such as **IoT logger** networks for groundwater monitoring and a connected **machine learning system and app**. The **BEST Adapt tool** evaluates flood risks and socio-economic factors to support evidence-based urban planning. These approaches improve decision-making by addressing diverse flood sources and aligning with residents' needs. It further aims to build transformative visions using flood-proof house designs and XR visualisations.

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Flood-proof **Demo Houses** showcase climate-resilient architecture, employing advanced materials and designs to withstand flooding while serving as a practical model for adaptation. **XR Pathfinder** is a web-based tool designed to help decision-makers choose suitable XR technologies for CCA planning and resilience initiatives. Collaboration with stakeholders ensures a shared vision for resilience. Through public consultations and inclusive tools, the LSD fosters trust and dialogue, aligning policies and practices with community needs. Together, these measures create a foundation for long-term climate resilience and transformative adaptation in the region. The solutions are introduced below and discussed in detail in Deliverable 3.12.

Table 2: Overview of available solutions by Central Denmark (RESIST Deliverable 3.12)

Name of solution	Solution type	Short description
IoT loggers	Tool for data collection	IoT loggers that can be used for assessment of local hydrology and monitoring of changes and development in the ground water table. This solution includes recommendations and support for the installation and maintenance of the loggers as well as support for data collection and stakeholder involvement.
XR Pathfinder	Digital/online tool	An online guide for public authorities containing guidelines on how to develop XR solutions and recommendations for using it in stakeholder involvement processes.
Demo houses	Physical constructions, Knowledge and experiences	2 physical demo houses testing materials and construction solutions regarding rising water levels and exposure to water in the flooding season. Knowledge exchange is provided both by accessibility of the houses on site in Lemvig combined with customized XR applications in the story telling.
Machine learning and app	Scientific and technical support	Processing of data collected from the IoT loggers through Machine Learning to identify patterns and tendencies in the data. The results are used in the development of a warning app that can warn citizens about ground water flooding.

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Socio-economic decision support tool – BEST Adapt	Digital, web-based; process tool	Decision support tool based on predicted flood maps, flood risks, and damage costs that calculates the socio-economic optimum CCA protection level of an area, including groundwater and recreational elements.
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4.1.1.3 Catalonia

Catalonia, ranging from the Mediterranean coasts to mountainous areas, faces a broad spectrum of climate hazards, including floods, heatwaves, droughts, forest fires with serious impact on the civil securities and supply of basic services. Social inequalities magnify the impacts, disproportionately affecting those more vulnerable to climate risks, such as the aging population, among others. The emergency-orientation in the civil protection lacks an integration of long-term adaptation processes, which highlights the lacking institutional capacity (see D1.11).

In RESIST, the work of the LSD in Catalonia addresses climate vulnerabilities through integrated strategies that enhance preparedness, improve emergency management, and engage communities. A key focus is to strengthen the multi-hazard **Argos Early Warning Systems** and introducing **impact-based Site-Specific Warning**, utilising localised risk data and real-time tools to support emergency responses. These systems, piloted in Blanes and Terrassa, enhance climate resilience by addressing local risks like coastal erosion, urban flooding, and heatwaves, while tailored alerts ensure effective communication and timely action.

Community engagement is central to the project, with a **Citizen Participatory Toolkit** designed to involve diverse groups, including vulnerable populations, in risk preparedness, emergency response and disaster recovery. This approach enhances inclusivity and builds trust. It is supported by education initiatives and citizen participatory processes that promote proactive responses to climate risks and collaboration among regional authorities, municipalities and communities at risk to strengthen local governance and resilience. The solutions are introduced below and discussed in detail in Deliverable 3.19.

Table 3: Overview of available solutions by Catalonia (RESIST Deliverable 3.19)

Name of solution	Solution type	Short description
Argos Early Warning System	Digital	Argos is an Early Warning System and a Decision Support Tool to help emergency managers and other stakeholders anticipate the impacts and better manage the weather-related emergencies that climate change is bringing. It

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Impact-based Site-Specific Warning		centralises all related information (hazard products in real-time and vulnerability elements), provides hyperlocal tailored early warnings on the specific critical points and infrastructures, and assists in situation management.
	Digital	Site-Specific Warning is a tool providing tailored information on risks that helps trigger action protocols or decisions for better managing the extreme weather-related emergency preparedness by different end-users at the local and community levels. It integrates the local data and knowledge at a specific vulnerable area, group, or infrastructure associated with extreme weather and climate events for tailored risk assessment and evaluation.
Citizen participatory toolkit in natural risks, climate change and civil protection	Practices and Methodologies	This toolkit is designed with a citizen-centric approach, aiming to strengthen communities by fostering inclusive participatory processes and social action addressing natural hazards, climate change and civil protection participation. This toolkit is built upon three fundamental pillars, each serving as a complementary lane of work to achieve our goal: 1) New methodologies and formats; 2) Inclusive risk communication guide; 3) Citizen dialogues methodology. In Catalonia, it is particularly intended for use by municipal civil protection teams or local decision-makers committed to promoting its implementation. However, it is also applicable at different levels of governance and within a diverse array of social organisations, regardless of their size or structure.

4.1.1.4 Central Portugal

The **Central Portugal** region, with the pilot areas of Coimbra and Médio Tejo, is exposed to severe risks from heatwaves, droughts, floods, and wildfires. Agriculture and forestry are increasingly vulnerable to shifting climatic conditions. Droughts and monoculture forestry practices heighten wildfire risks, while urban expansion disrupts natural drainage, intensifying flash floods. Socio-economic disparities exacerbate these vulnerabilities.

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In RESIST, Central Portugal focuses on transforming land use and forest management to create more resilient landscapes and sustainable practices. A key priority is biomass management, as excess biomass increases wildfire risks. By promoting responsible collection and introducing fire-resistant and economically valuable tree species, the project aims to mitigate fire hazards while enhancing biodiversity.

Community engagement plays a critical role, fostering stewardship among landowners and ensuring inclusive participation. Innovative approaches like **Village Condominiums** and **AIGP - Integrated Areas of Landscape Management** involve citizens, landowners, and authorities in co-creating participatory land management models. These models promote sustainable biomass practices, build social trust, and demonstrate resilience through integrated governance. The approach also emphasises developing a circular bioeconomy, **valorising biomass** for energy production and other uses such as fertilisers and bio-based materials. The solutions are introduced below and discussed in detail in Deliverable 3.24.

Table 4: Overview of available solutions by Central Portugal (RESIST Deliverable 3.24)

Name of solution	Solution type	Short description
AIGP - Integrated Areas for Landscape Management	Process and management practices	AIGP is a strategic approach to managing grouped land areas (over 100 hectares) to mitigate wildfire risks and enhance climate resilience. It focuses on landscape transformation, species reconversion, and territorial revitalisation, backed by structured financial and operational frameworks. Landowners or management entities are responsible for sustainable forest resource management. It integrates technical measures like fuel load reduction and protection zones with community engagement to create safer, more resilient landscapes. Long-term success requires key enablers: stakeholder engagement (workshops with forest owners and locals), land-use changes (evaluating and implementing management strategies such as fuel reduction and species replacement), new business models (promoting agroforestry species resilient to wildfires and climate change), and communication/training, particularly for forest firefighters.

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Village Condominium - Buffer zones for rural villages	Processes and management practices	Village Condominiums focus on establishing 100-meter buffer zones around rural communities to reduce wildfire risks and enhance climate resilience. These zones minimize fuel loads and create safe distances between vegetation and buildings, protecting residents. In areas like Central Portugal, this approach replaces unmanaged, flammable vegetation with native broadleaf species, reducing flammability and promoting biodiversity. For long-term impact, key enablers include stakeholder and community engagement (workshops with forest owners and locals), selecting fire-resistant species and land uses (fuel load reduction, species replacement, and forest improvement), new business models (promoting agroforestry and silvopastoralism), and communication/training, particularly for forest firefighters.
Valorisation of biomass for NbS and products (new)	Processes and management practices	Residual forest biomass can be valorised into valuable resources to reduce wildfire risk and create new business models through NbS (e.g., shredding and incorporation of the biomass into the soil, construction of live fascines and shelter structures), energy generation (heat and electricity), pellets and fertilisers (biochar) production.

To summarise the regional contexts: each region is facing distinct challenges, commonalities can be found on the level of the risks, consisting of flooding and water management, heat and drought risks, and ecosystem and biodiversity loss, and institutional and socio-economic vulnerabilities. A more detailed account of the regional environmental systems and the needs the regions face in the context of climate change can be found in the [Deliverable 1.1](#), Needs assessment for large-scale demonstrator regions. While the solutions are described in more detail in the Deliverables D3.4, D3.12, D3.19, and D3.24.

4.1.2 Building blocks for regional TSI strategies

4.1.2.1 Strategic actions under Key Focus Area 1

4.1.2.1.1 Adaptation platform

To ensure a long-term impact of RESIST, **institutionalising the project’s regional collaborations into regional adaptation platforms** is important to foster transformative climate adaptation and

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regional resilience. Currently, each of the LSDs themselves can be interpreted as (temporary) regional adaptation platform that brings together different partners to jointly develop and implement climate adaptation efforts. As such, the RESIST project provides an organisation that allows for coordinating, scaling, and sustaining climate adaptation efforts in their respective regions. To sustain these dynamics in the long-term, creating a formalised structure in the form of an adaptation platform can create an impact beyond the project’s lifetime. Through the implementation of a coordinative element, the **adaptation platforms can empower regional actors** in a transition from reactive to proactive agency and governance in adaptation processes through collective reflection processes ensure adaptation efforts’ innovative character.

In terms of the sustaining processes for these platforms as part of LSD activities, the main focus across all regions is on further **formalising collaborations** among municipalities, regional authorities, academia, and civil society. Thus, they can provide a foundation for increased cooperation, experimentation, and knowledge exchange, enabling municipalities to act as climate adaptation niches where innovative measures can continue to be piloted, resulting in transformative case-based learning in the regions. Also, emphasis should be put on these platforms abilities to continuously refine the regional adaptation strategies by promote collaborative learning and ensuring long-term inclusivity in decision-making.

In conclusion, well-structured platform, bringing regional key actors together in a shared forum, can be used to build up technical expertise, local knowledge, and community participation, ensuring that adaptation strategies are locally tailored and widely supported while also contributing to structured and effective adaptation efforts. As such, these platforms are in their current form to be seen as facilitators in the co-creation of RESIST solutions, specific to each LSD. With regards to the future, the focus is drawn to establishing recognised and balanced coordination hubs, engaging a wide variety of stakeholders, incl. local governments, research institutions, community organisations, and the private sector to support capacity-building, data-sharing, and resource mobilisation.

Table 5: Operationalisation of the Key Focus Area 1: Dynamics within the LSDs

	Objective	Strategic actions	Links
Key Focus Area	To strengthen and maintain collaborative dynamics within LSDs teams as a mechanism for fostering sustainable empowerment and shared	Adaptation platform: Establish and expand a platform that collectively and sustainability drives regional transformative adaptation by bringing together relevant actors, power relations, and competences.	Task 1.2 - GDT framework and deployment

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<p>directionality. TSI strategies need to enable collective, context-specific responses to transformative climate adaptation, depending on agency, empowerment, and reflexive learning.</p>	<p>Capacities: Mobilise the collective capacities of the platform members, so it gains agency to effectively utilise its members’ roles within the region, their access to internal and external resources, and their competences and skills.</p> <p>Reflexive learning: Implement open and participatory formats to equip actors with reflexive knowledge of their actions and changing contexts, which is essential for the governance of complex, non-linear and emerging transformative processes.</p>	
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4.1.2.1.2 Capacities

A key priority for RESIST is to recognise and strategically develop the capacities of its collaborating partners across LSDs, ensuring that they are well-equipped to lead and sustain transformative adaptation efforts. Within the context of the RESIST LSDs, this type of **capacity-building** is not just about technical training, it is strongly engaged with strengthening municipal agency and **fostering long-term leadership in climate adaptation**. The project’s focus on empowering collaborating partners provides a good basis for ensuring that adaptation strategies remain actionable, sustainable, and adaptable to local and regional needs.

To amplify this, targeted project meetings on the specific topics of the LSD are a key activity that the TSI strategies focus on. Peer-to-peer exchanges play a crucial role in facilitating knowledge-sharing, allowing partners to learn from each other and ensuring that adaptation solutions remain context-specific and responsive to the environmental and social realities of each LSD. Beyond that, capacity-building also reinforces municipal leadership and ownership over adaptation initiatives. Furthermore, by equipping LSD collectives with the necessary expertise, decision-making tools, and governance strategies, RESIST strengthens their ability to navigate complex multi-level governance.

In the end, TSI strategies emphasise the notion that reinforcement of confidence through capacity building can foster long-term engagement and responsibility, empowering local actors to take proactive roles in adaptation governance and implementation. The adaptation platforms mentioned above can help in this process and serve as vehicle for integrating different resources, roles and skills, to build up collective capacities to refine strategies, strengthen cooperation, and enhance trust across regional partners.

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4.1.2.1.3 Reflexive Learning

Finally, reflexive learning within the project's collaborating partners and, later, within the adaptation platform is essential for ensuring that **adaptation approaches remain dynamic, responsive, and continuously improving**. Thus, across regions, TSI strategies emphasise the need for creating structured spaces for knowledge exchange. These enable municipalities, academia, and industry partners to document experiences, evaluate progress, and iteratively refine adaptation approaches. This process ensures that insights gained from implementation inform future strategies, allowing for ongoing adaptation and adjustment based on real-world outcomes.

One key mechanism for fostering reflexive learning can be found in the regular exchanges among project partners. In this context, reflexive learning is not just about knowledge-sharing but also works to **create an adaptive, self-improving system** that continuously refines its strategies based on real-world insights and collaborative reflection. By emphasising this aspect, exchanges can facilitate the transdisciplinary combination of scientific expertise with community-based knowledge. The use of the RESIST **Graphical Digital Twins** (GDT, T1.2) can support the communication and reflection on different planning options or impacts within the regional contexts. This reflexive approach not only enhances the technical and governance aspects of adaptation but potentially also strengthen social inclusivity in planning processes. As such, it can play a key role in strengthening stakeholder engagement to ensure that adaptation strategies are inclusive and contextually grounded.

In areas that are key to RESIST such as sustainable land management, wildfire mitigation, and flood resilience, reflective, iterative processes can ultimately support the scaling of best practices and the development of more robust, evidence-based strategies. Furthermore, by documenting and sharing successes and lessons learned across regional and international networks, the project contributes to broader climate adaptation efforts beyond its immediate scope.

4.1.2.2 Strategic actions under Key Focus Area 2

4.1.2.2.1 Creating networks

As already explained in Key Focus Area 1, RESIST has a rather strong emphasis on strengthening local networks in the regions by bringing together administration, incl. municipal and regional authorities, civil protections agencies, with businesses, academia, and civil society and environmental organisations. In their current configuration, these **alliances contribute to overcoming existing fragmentations** through coordinated, inclusive, and community-driven activities. By ensuring that these networks are participatory, regions can build adaptive systems that persist and establish well-integrated responses to climate risks.

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Table 6: Operationalisation of the Key Focus Area 2: Network formation beyond the LSDs

	Objective	Strategic actions	Links
Key Focus Area 2	To strategically expand the regional and international networks to enable the collaborative governance, inclusivity, and multi-level coordination. The creation of inclusive narratives of adaptation is central to unify stakeholders around shared objectives and encouraging replication across regions and sectors.	<p>Creating networks: Actively engage in the develop of regional and international networks to align local actors, policymakers, and international frameworks, and to enable participatory and cross-sectoral collaboration for transformative adaptation.</p> <p>Diffusion of solutions: Create strategies for increasing the user-base of innovative solutions through scaling, replicating, or generalising of successful adaptation initiatives as a means of creating translocal experiences and establishing innovation systems around those adaptation efforts.</p> <p>Narrative: Foster inclusive narratives of change that support the creation of networks and diffusion of solutions by creating awareness, unifying stakeholders, and driving community buy-in.</p>	<p>T1.1 – Upscaling LSD solutions to other EU regions are instrumental for expanding networks</p> <p>T2.1 – Both CoP and Col are focused on mutual learning and the sharing of challenges both within and beyond RESIST</p> <p>T5.4 – Efforts to build external relations, particularly the collaboration with other EU projects and relevant EU / national initiatives</p>

Looking into the future, the mentioned project activities provide a great basis for broadening networks and mobilise their transformative potential. Further, these activities are complemented by activities (T2.1) that establish **Communities of Practice, Communities of Interest**, or regional **Twinning Schemes** in WP3, that provide organised approaches to further network formation. Based on that, strong emphasis on structurally embedding current connections, for instance into governance structures, funding mechanisms, and participatory frameworks needs to accompany these project activities. In this way, increasingly formalised networks can be pivotal to secure long-term adaptation funding, strengthen cross-sector collaboration, and ultimately ensure that climate adaptation remains a core regional priority rather than a temporary initiative. Also, beyond local and regional networks, international partnerships are recommended to exchange best practices, access funding, and co-

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develop adaptation solutions. Also here, the connections that RESIST helps to build in a European context, can be a forceful driver of the networking process.

In the regions, these actions for network building need to take various forms, based on the LSD aims. In Southwest Finland, the aim is to bring together municipalities, academia, civil society, and planning bodies to support and strengthen long-term cooperation. Focusing on increased water-management capabilities and its necessity for multiple stakeholders to be included, peer-to-peer exchanges and capacity-building initiatives can help building these networks to strengthen adaptation efforts. In Central Denmark, the networking efforts are initially a way of sharing knowledge and re-aligning different local actors with new realities that climate change has caused in terms of water management. The different frontier technological solutions in the region, function as tools to build transformative alliances among municipal actors, businesses, and community organisations. In Catalonia, it involves structured coordination between emergency services and local governance actors, thus refining communication strategies and operational frameworks to better align with local realities and expectations. These networks can serve as a mechanism for scaling, replicating, and circulating successful adaptation solutions in emergency management. Finally, in Central Portugal the local consortium has multiple partners involved in demonstrating the potential of these solutions and connecting to experts also beyond the local level, thus providing a good basis for the systemic integration into long-term resilience planning.

4.1.2.2.2 Diffusion of solutions

Supporting the diffusion of adaptation solutions is one of the strategic actions of the TSI as well as for the RESIST project itself (see T1.1). To create impact, it is central to go beyond a structured approach to documentation, knowledge transfer, and policy integration but to also establish mechanisms for knowledge-sharing and strategic alignment with policy frameworks, within the regions and beyond. A key advantage here is that successful **solutions are assessed, shared, and replicated** across regions through case studies, structured networks, and training initiatives in different RESIST WPs. This provides an excellent framework for diffusion. However, there is a need to embed these solutions into regional, national, and EU adaptation strategies, which would provide the foundation for their long-term impact through ensuring local pilots and become scalable and transformative models in multiple contexts.

The actions for diffusion include specific measures. In Southwest Finland, this might build on peer-to-peer exchanges and training programmes, ensuring that different stakeholders become aware of the possible solutions, thus implementing them into regional planning frameworks and strategies. For Central Denmark, RESIST's twinning and exploitation schemes serve as structured pathways for replicating adaptation solutions across different municipalities. Adaptation solutions such as

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Demo Houses and IoT Loggers are reviewed for replicability, ensuring that technical specifications, impact assessments, and lessons learned are made accessible to wider groups of stakeholders. In Catalonia, actions should aim at spreading the solutions through municipal and public service networks. Finally, in Central Portugal the focus is on highlighting the economic, social, and environmental benefits of its different solutions on a local level. This serves as a mechanism for scaling, replicating, and circulating successful adaptation solutions.

The TSI strategies' focus on ensuring that adaptation solutions are not only tested but also systematically shared, scaled, and embedded into governance structures. This should create a foundation for lasting transformative impact. This approach transforms localised innovations into transferable models, reinforcing the broader goal of making climate adaptation both actionable and enduring across diverse regional contexts

4.1.2.2.3 Strengthening narratives

The development of narratives of adaptive climate action can serve as empowering and unifying process, **gathering stakeholders and partners around recognisable and shared visions**. They, thus, support the network formation by making adaptation more tangible and relatable. Further, strengthening narrative helps designing inclusive, accessible, and participatory communication campaigns. By weaving narratives around local realities, these regions can create stronger public engagement and ownership of adaptation efforts. With regards to activities in other Key Focus Areas, narrative framing helps to have lasting impact, by explicitly trying to embed these narratives into institutional communication strategies and public engagement initiatives. Thus, by making adaptation efforts visible, interactive, and widely communicated, these regions ensure that narratives drive long-term behavioural and policy change.

To provide some examples from LSDs, in Southwest Finland this can involve the linking of NbS to cultural identity and historical land use, making adaptation feel like a natural extension of local traditions. Central Denmark can be seen as taking an immersive approach, where it uses XR Pathfinder to create interactive experiences that visually communicate climate risks and adaptation opportunities. Also, projects like Demo Houses and IoT Loggers serve as physical storytelling tools, illustrating how climate adaptation can be integrated into everyday life. In Catalonia, adaptation communication and is structured around multilingual, culturally relevant narratives, ensuring that emergency preparedness efforts reach diverse and vulnerable populations. While, in Central Portugal, this entails a focus on co-creating adaptation narratives with landowners and communities, ensuring that their concerns are reflected in the way adaptation efforts are framed.

All these approaches make adaptation not just a technical challenge, but a shared societal mission. Thus, by embedding adaptation within **cultural, technological, and community-driven narratives**,

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regions can foster a deeper sense of collective responsibility. Rather than being perceived as distant policy measures, adaptation efforts become lived experiences rooted in identity, shared through immersive tools, and reinforced by local engagement. This narrative-driven approach not only helps strengthening immediate adaptation efforts but also lays the groundwork for enduring resilience, ensuring that climate adaptation remains a priority across generations.

4.1.2.3 Strategic actions under Key Focus Area 3

Table 7: Operationalisation of the Key Focus Area 3: Catalysing institutional change through the LSD

	Objective	Strategic actions	Links
Key Focus Area 3	<p>To influence institutional change by challenging entrenched norms and structures, promoting alternative governance models, as foundation of facilitating transformative adaptation processes. Addressing systemic lock-ins is key to support broader change and sustainable development in the long term.</p>	<p>Challenge unsustainable practices: Identify, challenge, and renegotiate the frameworks, cognitive models, identities, roles, and arrangements that enable unsustainable behaviours and routines to break lock-ins and enable the emergence of alternative approaches.</p> <p>Institutionalise adaptation: Supporting the uptake of adaptive solutions requires favourable institutional framework conditions, including budgets, operational routines, and long-term planning, that ensure its position as a central priority for public and private sectors.</p> <p>New logics: Identify and strengthen alternative logics to addressing climate vulnerabilities that are inherent to the developed transformative solutions and support their implementation in governance and diffusion contexts.</p>	<p>T1.1 – Co-creation & design workshops</p> <p>T1.2 – GDT simulations</p> <p>T4.3 – Virtual Interactive Exhibits</p>

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4.1.2.3.1 Challenge unsustainable practices

This step is concerned with **identifying and exposing the systemic inefficiencies** that reinforce vulnerability to climate risks. A prominent example here are policies related to practices central to adaptation, like urban planning, land management, and disaster response. These need to be analysed to identify barriers to change. Furthermore, in most regions it also involves a need to rethink traditional perceptions of disaster and risk, moving beyond purely technological fixes and instead acknowledging the socio-environmental dimensions of resilience. Within the context of RESIST, the Needs Assessment (T1.1) has already played an important role in this regard, and the recommendations of the TSI build on these findings.

Pivotal here are efforts to **introduce transformative alternatives that embed sustainability into decision-making frameworks**. In the RESIST LSDs this most prominently involves examples like the design regional adaptation strategies that integrate NbS (especially Southwest Finland, but also in Central Denmark and Central Portugal), adaptive land-use policies (Southwest Finland, Central Denmark, Central Portugal), and governance reforms that prioritise long-term resilience (all LSDs). Furthermore, economic incentives, such as ecosystem service rewards (Central Portugal), cooperative land management schemes, and policy-driven financial support, can drive change or lock-in unsustainable behaviour. To support transformations, these instruments are key to ensure that adaptation efforts are both viable and attractive to key stakeholders as basis for accelerating shifts towards sustainable behaviour. In this way, these alternatives can contribute to institutional transformation, while they push the reform of outdated regulatory structures to accommodate new approaches.

Finally, for these changes to be lasting, they must be **embraced collectively by local authorities, businesses, and civil society**. Here there is a pivotal role for participatory decision-making efforts. In RESIST this can be achieved through the planned workshops, policy dialogues, and community engagement initiatives, which create space for collaborative problem-solving (T1.1, T4.3). Furthermore, cross-sector alliances, particularly between municipalities, academia, and NGOs, can help ensure that expertise is shared, and adaptation efforts are informed by the latest research and best practices. Finally, also demonstration projects and digital tools, such as Digital Twin technology (T1.2, all LSDs) and VR/XR simulations (currently in Central Denmark, but potentially also in other LSDs), can be instrumental in visualising impacts of unsustainable and sustainable adaptation scenarios. By making the case for transformation through tangible examples, these tools can help build trust, strengthen institutional commitment, and reinforce long-term sustainability goals.

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4.1.2.3.2 Institutionalise adaptation

A crucial step for any innovative approach is its institutionalisation through its integration into **social practices, organisational routines, or governance structures**. In RESIST LSDs this is applied by working to integrate the adaptation plans to the regional, municipal, and organisational level. Here, TSI strategies aim at implementation of adaptation priorities to new and existing policies, ensuring that resilience-building is not treated as a separate, temporary initiative but as a core element of governance.

In general, this is achieved by aligning climate adaptation efforts with existing legal and regulatory structures or cultural routines while also advocating for reforms that make adaptation a mandatory and continuous process rather than an optional add-on. To support this process, there is an emphasis on using innovative digital tools are leveraged to enhance decision-making. Great examples from RESIST are Digital Twin technology (T1.3, all LSDs) and XR & VR simulations (Central Denmark), and the development of the intuitive AGROS Early Warning System (Catalonia). These technologies allow stakeholders to better understand climate risks, simulate adaptation scenarios, and assess the long-term impacts of different policy choices. While the BEST Adapt tool for socio-economic decision support (Central Denmark), and the cost-benefit analysis (Southwest Finland) are examples of informing policy making directly.

At the same time, participatory approaches such as training programmes and capacity-building initiatives can be instrumental, as they help to ingrain adaptation in organisational cultures (T1.1). By fostering a mindset shift within municipal governance, the private sector, and public agencies, organisations can move from reactive responses to proactive, preventive adaptation strategies. This can help to overcome sectoral silos and foster collaboration between different actors. Thus, strengthening these partnerships ensures that adaptation is approached holistically, drawing on diverse expertise and resources. Organisational commitment is further reinforced by developing long-term networks, encouraging knowledge-sharing, and promoting best practices across regions.

4.1.2.3.3 Establishing new logics

Finally, the establishment of new logics is relevant in all regions in the sense that there is a clear need to reframe adaptation beyond traditional, reactive approaches. This builds first and foremost on the promotion of new adaptation paradigms. Furthermore, another emphasis across regions is on community-centred decision-making that helps challenge traditional, top-down approaches and ensures that adaptation is tailored to local realities. In practice, the active involvement of landowners, civil society, and local organisations in adaptation planning, can not only help to enhance legitimacy but also help establish these new logics.

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Innovative solutions from the regions can very much function as catalysers in this regard. For instance, adaptive and floating housing in flood-prone areas (Central Denmark), integration of NbS as standard planning tools (Southwest Finland), and embedding resilience into land and emergency management strategies. In short, rather than treating adaptation as a separate process, new logics encourage a shift towards systemic, pre-emptive, and integrated solutions that align with social, environmental, and economic priorities.

The most difficult part here is to **ensure the long-term viability of these logics**, requiring them to be translated into institutional frameworks, financial incentives, and regulatory standards. Across the regions, the focus is to align innovations with legal frameworks, municipal planning, and investment priorities to ensure that the novel solutions have a higher chance of becoming scalable, replicable, and economically feasible.

4.1.2.4 Strategic actions under Key Focus Area 4

Table 8: Operationalisation of the Key Focus Area 4: Shaping the socio-material context

	Objective	Strategic actions	Links
Key Focus Area 4	To examine the interplay between transformative adaptation efforts and their socio-material context as a basis for navigating path-dependent infrastructures and socio-ecological vulnerabilities. Fostering resilience and adaptive capacities will ultimately depend on a successful transformation of the material configuration of regional societies.	<p>Transform socio-material context: To increase resilience of local and regional communities, their socio-material context, consisting of interconnected physical exposures and social vulnerabilities, needs to be adapted through the novel approaches reshaping practices and environment.</p> <p>Path-dependencies: To overcome path-dependencies in infrastructure development and management of cultural landscapes during transformative adaptation efforts, historical developments, local knowledge, and cultural practices can be leveraged to reduce vulnerabilities.</p>	Development of solutions in the LSDs as outlined in WP3

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4.1.2.4.1 Transform socio-material context

Transforming the socio-material context is an inherently long-term process that demands persistent engagement and structural shifts over time and might **relate to the project's impacts**. In many ways, this extends beyond the efforts in the RESIST project and could materialise as the project's impacts. Thus, it is important to push for this type of ambitious transformation. Across RESIST regions this can start through a combination of integrating local expertise, research-driven insights, and material adaptation practices to develop place-based, climate-resilient solutions.

Each region has its own opportunities in this regard. For example, in Southwest Finland, integrating NbS into cultural landscapes reinforces long-term environmental and social resilience by connecting adaptation efforts to local traditions. In Central Denmark, its design of interactive, demonstrable flood adaptation solutions can set new planning standards. Similarly, in Catalonia, modernising emergency management tools ensures that institutional frameworks evolve alongside the material systems that support them. In Central Portugal, this involves biomass valorisation and circular bioeconomy initiatives that promote sustainable land use and forest management in the long run.

In virtually all these instances, transforming the socio-material **context requires rethinking infrastructure as well as land-use systems** to better align with adaptation needs. Furthermore, it also hinges on continuous efforts of collaborative planning and co-created adaptation frameworks, ensuring that new climate solutions work within and enhance existing material environments. These approaches not only improve resilience but also foster economic sustainability by aligning adaptation with financial incentives and long-term land stewardship models. Finally, transforming the material context is not just about infrastructure, it is about shifting routines and practices. For that, activities in other Key Focus Areas can be mobilised embed adaptive solutions into tangible, everyday environments.

4.1.2.4.2 Path-dependencies

Finally, a key theme across regions is the recognition that historical policies, practices, and perceptions **shape contemporary adaptation efforts and the opportunity space for diverging from past developments**. In terms of transformation, rather than treating this historical context as an obstacle, many regions can leverage past experiences to inform better decision-making and use this knowledge as well as cultural narratives to build more context-sensitive adaptation strategies. Recognising and incorporating these historical trajectories increases the legitimacy, effectiveness, and local ownership of adaptation initiatives. Across all regions, adaptation efforts must build upon history, ensuring that new strategies acknowledge past constraints while embedding more sustainable, flexible, and locally relevant solutions.

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Also here, it is useful to provide some examples from the LSDs to provide more insights into the consequences of this issue. In short, in Southwest Finland this concerns a focus on integrating local ecological knowledge and traditional land use practices into contemporary adaptation efforts, ensuring that solutions align with cultural and environmental realities. In Central Denmark, this means critically analysing past flood protection policies and urban planning frameworks to understand their long-term impact on resilience. In Catalonia, this involves studying past disaster events and community responses to refine risk communication and build trust in emergency management. Finally, in Central Portugal, historical land ownership structures and forestry policies have contributed to governance fragmentation and unsustainable land management.

In all cases, adaptation efforts must address these inherited constraints rather than simply applying new solutions on top of inadequate systems. This requires systemic policy shifts that move beyond individual land management and towards collective resilience strategies. Across regions, the key is acknowledging historical constraints while creating the institutional flexibility needed for transformative adaptation.

4.2 Outlook and implementation

4.2.1 Outlook

Synthesising the building blocks introduced above, represent a foundational step in initiating a long-term, transformative process aimed at addressing regional vulnerabilities and enhancing adaptive capacities in the RESIST regions to complement the other project activities. As such, the implementation of such a process requires the creation of new arenas, a focus on experimentation, and agile governance aiming to build up transformative capacities and sustain an ongoing engagement with risks and vulnerabilities beyond the project's lifetime. In this context, with its theoretically grounded framework, the TSI provides the basis for regional development processes that connect regional adaption efforts with questions of social and systemic change.

While the TSI has been developed with the LSD regions, their challenge and activities within RESIST in mind, there is a need to further prioritise, contextualise and embed the suggested strategic actions in the regional governance context to successfully institutionalisation of change and to establish dedicated ownership of the process from regional partners within the LSD teams and beyond. This further necessitates an orientation towards participatory governance as the dynamic nature of transformation processes require continuous dialogue, flexibility, and alignment with evolving socio-political, environmental, and technological contexts.

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While the RESIST project provides regional partners with a limited mandate and agency to push this process forward, the LSD teams can also rely on the ongoing support and collaboration with transversal partners. The involvement of partners such as ZSI, through training, monitoring or formative evaluation processes can support regional partners by providing guidance, fostering capacity-building initiatives, and ensuring that the strategies remain adaptive to future uncertainties. Iterative evaluation and prioritisation processes will lay the groundwork for the RESIST project to foster impactful interventions that align transformative capacities with overarching adaptation goals. The project's contributions to social innovation will be documented in a forthcoming report (D4.1.3), that will reflect on the project's contribution catalysing a self-sustaining momentum that empowers regional governance systems to continually adapt and innovate.

4.2.2 Supporting the implementation and evaluating the impact

As described above, the implementation of such a transformative process is a non-linear and iterative process that intervenes into complex adaptive systems as each region's climate adaptation system is shaped by many organisations and actors that dynamically interact, learn, and, thus, produce emergent behaviours through decentralised interactions rather than centralised control. The steering of such systems, consequently, depends on tentative governance of public and private interventions rather than assertive and persistent ones (Kuhlmann et al., 2019). Implementing a project in such a context necessitates iterative development, flexible planning, reflexivity, and responsiveness to changing contexts. Keeping this complexity in mind, the following workplan to support the embedding of recommended action points in the work of the LSDs has been derived from the grant agreement:

4.2.2.1 Actions for the year 2025

Activities planned for implementation by June 2025 (M30):

- ZSI will prepare and send out a questionnaire to the four LSD regions to prioritise the strategic action points as elaborated in this report for further refinement. The questionnaire will be defined in close collaboration with the LSD leaders and be distributed by them.
- ZSI will join the LSD meetings to present the TSI documents and the results of the questionnaire and to co-creatively select the most important action points for each LSD. We suggest picking up to three strategic actions (e.g., narratives of change) per region, covering the key focus areas 1 to 3 each for a detailed elaboration and implementation work.
- These strategic actions, and the regional contextualisation of these issues for each LSD, are further elaborated, including concrete actions for implementation, by ZSI and the LSD teams.

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- ZSI will monitor and evaluate the process by analysing recordings from LSD meetings and finding opportunities to implement monitoring meetings within these or outside the planned LSD meetings, focusing on understanding dynamics of actions that could relate to the strategic action points as outlined in this document.
- Based on this strategy ZSI reinforces its availability to support regional partners from LSDs and Twinning regions in supporting the social engagement and innovation process.

Milestone: Strategic action points for further refinement selected (M30).

Activities planned for implementation by December 2025 (M36):

- ZSI will analyse the recordings of the LSD meetings and implement monitoring sessions as a part of the monitoring and formative evaluation process.
- ZSI will, in coordination with T1.1, providing trainings for the LSD and Twinning regions on visioning, co-creation and Transition Management during the GA in Catalonia, in October 2025 (M34).
- ZSI will finalise a concept to capture the social impact of the TSI processes in the LSDs. This document will present the main outcome categories, building on quantifiable indicators where possible, methods, key evaluative dimensions, and data collection approaches.

Milestones: Training delivered (M34), Impact concept developed (M36).

Figure 3: Timeline for TSI implementation in 2025

4.2.2.2 Actions for the year 2026

- ZSI will host an online co-creation workshop with each LSD team to reflect on current implementation of the strategic actions and steps to be taken in 2026.

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- ZSI will continue to monitor the LSD meetings and the regional social innovation processes and assess their social impact through formative and summative evaluations. If changes in the meeting rhythm should arise ZSI organise specific meetings.
- ZSI prepares and sends out a second iteration of the questionnaire to identify progress made and challenges faced in the implementation of the regional strategic actions.
- Reflections and learnings of the LSD regions will be summarized and shared with the twinning regions in an online workshop format during their development period

Milestones: co-creation WS conducted (M38), questionnaire sent (M47), online WS implemented (M48).

4.2.2.3 Actions for the year 2027

- ZSI continues to assess the LSD and TSI progress in the context of the monitoring and formative evaluation.
- ZSI organises on-site visits and reflection workshops in each LSD region by M50.
- During the on-site visit, a co-creation WS in each LSD region is organised to discuss the future of the TSI process beyond the project's lifespan.
- ZSI sends out the final iteration of the LSD questionnaires to capture impacts of the TSI process and identify issues for future recommendations, by M53.
- ZSI drafts and finalises the D4.1.2 - Social Impact Assessment by M55
- ZSI drafts and finalises the D4.1.3 - Report on TSI Co-Creation Workshops and social innovation processes by M60.

Milestones: on-site visits completed (M50), co-creation WS conducted (M50), final questionnaire sent out (M53).

Given the emergence of transformative approaches as outlined above, this provisional workplan will be adapted to reality should the need arise.

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5 Conclusion

This report aims to support a sustained transformative adaption approach in the four LSD regions Southwest Finland, Central Denmark, Catalonia, and Central Portugal as a basis for maximising the societal impact of RESIST. Based on a theoretically grounded approach to transformation and adaption to climate change, the report presents an approach that goes beyond technological innovation and understands transformation as changes in socio-technical and socio-ecological systems. It introduces the concept of transformative social innovation as a process perspective rather than an analytical one, which represents a conceptual novelty. Based on this understanding, a set of strategic actions have been co-produced with regional project partners. These actions are organised around the four key focus areas:

Table 9: Overview of the Key Focus Areas, their objectives and strategic actions

	Objective	Strategic actions
Key Focus Area 1	To strengthen and maintain collaborative dynamics within LSDs teams as a mechanism for fostering sustainable empowerment and shared directionality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adaptation platform • Capacities • Reflexive learning
Key Focus Area 2	To strategically expand the regional and international networks and enable collaborative governance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create networks • Diffusion of solutions • Strengthening narratives
Key Focus Area 3	To influence institutional change for facilitating transformative adaptation processes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Challenge unsustainable practices • Institutionalise adaptation • Establishing new logics
Key Focus Area 4	To examine the interplay between transformative adaptation efforts and their socio-material context	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transform socio-material context • Path-dependencies

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The challenge of maximising the impact of regional climate adaptation efforts in the context of the RESIST project lies in the inherent complexity and multidimensionality of climate change and the regional responses. The core challenge for regions across Europe, which face diverse and interconnected climate risks and socio-economic vulnerabilities, is that conventional adaptation frameworks often fall short in addressing the systemic and transformative changes required. Incremental solutions, while necessary, lack the capacity to deinstitutionalise existing socio-technical and socio-ecological vulnerabilities that reinforce climate risks. Consequently, there is an urgent need for approaches that overcome sectoral silos and foster resilience through innovative governance, participatory processes, and social equity.

In this context, this report is a first step in supporting the RESIST regions in maximising the social impact of project activities through the provision of a transformative perspective. The report provides a conceptual novelty as it utilises Transformative Social Innovation theory not merely as an analytical tool but as a guiding framework for informing regional climate adaptation policy. TSI theory, with its emphasis on systemic change, relational governance, and collective empowerment, has traditionally been applied to analyse social innovations within academic settings. However, this report operationalises TSI as a normative and strategic framework to design and implement transformative regional climate adaptation strategies and, thus, embeds TSI in policies for addressing climate adaptation challenges. The approach builds strategic actions in the four key focus areas summarised in Table 9. These actions represent critical areas that need to be addressed, to create transformative outcomes and empower regional actors to drive systemic change.

The key focus area of dynamics within the LSD recognises the socio-political nature of climate adaptation, focusing on creating sustainable structures that foster participatory governance and co-creation processes beyond the lifetime of the project. Network formation emphasises collaboration and knowledge exchange across sectors, scales, and regions, facilitating the alignment of local actions with broader policy frameworks. Institutional change addresses the structural barriers that impede transformative adaptation by advocating for adaptive, reflexive, and inclusive governance arrangements. Finally, socio-material transformation aims to align technological and infrastructural trajectories with social and ecological contexts, ensuring that adaptation measures are both technically robust and reduce vulnerabilities.

By applying the TSI framework across these diverse contexts, the project will demonstrate its applicability and versatility as a tool for informing regional adaptation policy. This approach not only addresses the immediate challenges of climate adaptation but also creates conditions for long-term systemic transformation. The emphasis on co-creation, inclusivity, and multi-level coordination ensures that regional strategies are both contextually relevant and aligned with broader sustainability goals.

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